

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES INC.

10th
ANNUAL REPORT
for the year ended June 30, 1966

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1028 Connecticut Avenue, N.W., Washington, D. C. 20036

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* Chancellor Wells was succeeded by President Cole as a Member of the Executive Committee on December 11, 1965.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

Ten Years: 1956-1966

AN INGENIOUS READING-DESK.

INTRODUCTION

The Tenth Year, 1965-1966

The Council's tenth year, which ended on June 30, 1966 saw the completion of a number of important projects that had received the Council's assistance as well as the commencement of others that may be expected to have similar interest and importance.

Among projects completed were the Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives convened in Washington in May 1966 to promote freedom of access to the world's archival resources for historical research; completion of work on the Anglo-American cataloging code; publication of the massive 3d edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada*, of Dr. Keyes D. Metcalf's awaited book on *Planning Academic and Research Library Buildings*, and of the long-needed collaboratively developed manual on *Library Statistics: A Handbook of Standards and Terminology*.

Among projects begun was the pilot demonstration known as MARC (MACHine-Readable Catalog) for the distribution of Library of Congress cataloging information in machine-readable form to 16 primary and a much larger number of secondary participating libraries; an investigation of the factors affecting the use in libraries of microfacsimile at high reduction ratios (100x or more); an investigation of methods for replacing the worn-out card catalog of a principal research library; and arrangements for the publication of a list of books for college libraries to complement the current book selection service, *Choice*, which now is in its third year with the Council's assistance.

These projects, and others completed or commenced during the year, are described in greater detail in the following pages.

Thirty-three grants and contracts were made by the Council in the amount of \$1,150,075 in the fiscal year that ended on June 30, 1966. Twenty-six of the allocations were for new projects while seven were for extensions or renewals of previously-supported activities.

The Years, 1956-1966

The Council came into being on September 18, 1956, the date being that of its organization meeting as a non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia. Its purpose, as stated in its articles of incorporation, was "to aid in the solution of library problems."

There was an extended background to that meeting. The libraries of the country were at the time facing the increasing urgencies of post-War demands in terms of swollen student enrollments, the proliferation and diversification of research and development with increasing dependence upon library resources, all in the face of rising costs and a rising flood of publication. But they were facing these demands still largely dependent upon pre-War buildings, staffs, book-funds and procedures and were as well very self-conscious about the high cost of modernization. Although the years immediately preceding had brought some important improvements (for example, the development of the Farmington Plan for the cooperative acquisition of foreign publications, the demonstration of cooperative storage warehousing in the Midwest Inter Library Center — now the Center for Research Libraries, the perfecting of photo lithography which among other things made possible the return of the book-form catalog, and the introduction of office copying devices) yet the fact remained that libraries were falling far short of their own goals as well as the expectations of their users and that assistance was clearly needed.

It was, however, difficult to say just what form assistance should take. By some it was felt that libraries were neglecting to take advantage of modern technology, and they pointed to the potential space-saving characteristics of microfilm and to the information storage and retrieval capabilities of those "giant brains," the computers, as calling for more effective exploitation than libraries were giving them.

For several years the Ford Foundation had been conducting an inquiry into the problems of libraries and had come to the conclusion that financial support was only one of these — that other problems would face the library and the scholar who uses it even if money for buildings and books were limitlessly available. In the course of its inquiry the Foundation requested Dr. Louis B. Wright, the Director

of the Folger Shakespeare Library, as the chairman of a committee whose other members were Dr. Leonard Carmichael, the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution, and Mr. L. Quincy Mumford, the Librarian of Congress, to convene a group to discuss these problems. In consequence, two meetings were held at the Folger Library in January and March 1955, assembling some fifty representatives of many professions concerned with libraries, whether as librarians or users of libraries or as administrators of larger organizations of which libraries were a part.

This group widely explored the various approaches to the problems of libraries. Perhaps its central conclusion was that libraries, though suffering from the effects of the machine age, had gained disproportionately little from these effects, in part at least because of the relatively small market offered by libraries for specialized labor-saving devices. It was agreed that the situation called for the establishment of an independent body, free to attack the various problems of libraries through research, development, coordination of effort or otherwise. Recommendations to that effect were submitted by Dr. Wright to the Foundation on behalf of the group in April 1955, and their essentials were embodied in action taken by the Foundation a year later when, by resolution of the Trustees on June 18-19, 1956, it established the Council.

It is worthy of remark that on the second of these days, June 19, 1956, President Eisenhower signed the Federal Library Services Act into law. This Act, the first expression of Federal interest in a national library service, provided for demonstrations in rural areas lacking library facilities. The assignment of the Council, by contrast, was to determine new attacks upon the traditional problems involved in the storage and dissemination of knowledge, to encourage new methods, to promote inter-library cooperation and the pooling of reservoirs of little-used materials in the interest of greater availability, and to encourage the coordination of library work even across national boundaries.

To direct this program the members of the Council, initially 12 (now 13) in number, were selected to represent the public interest in libraries rather than a professional or other particular view. For example, the chairman of the Council from its establishment until his resignation in 1965

was Mr. Gilbert W. Chapman, the head of a well-known manufacturing corporation, but also simultaneously the president of the board of trustees of a great public library and active in many other groups concerned with the improvement of both academic and public library service.

For the work of the Council, the Foundation made an initial grant of \$5 million for a five-year period and in December 1960 extended this with a second grant of \$8 million for a further seven-to-ten year period. An additional nearly half million dollars has derived from interest on investments as well as from a gift from the Framlingham Foundation.

In ten years the Council has made 346 grants and other allocations, representing a somewhat smaller number of projects and totalling approximately \$8.5 million. This was at the average rate of approximately 35 grants a year, in an average amount of somewhat less than \$25,000.

Limitations upon program

Although the assignment "to aid in the solution of library problems" suggests an almost limitless scope of activity, certain bounds quickly impose themselves in practice. For example, it is obvious that the problems with which a program such as that of the Council should concern itself are those which affect numbers of libraries or even libraries generally, and not the purely local problems which hamper individual institutions—such as the need for buildings, books or staff—and which almost invariably result from insufficient funds rather than lack of knowledge. To such local needs the Council's total resources would of course be but a drop in the bucket.

Similarly, while it is incontestable that library work is based upon bibliography and that bibliographical improvements have been responsible for major advances, yet projects of potentially useful bibliographical work are so numerous that some criterion is necessary in order to force a selection. The criterion adopted by the Council limits consideration of such projects to those that promise either the development of new technique or of improved access to important resources of wide or general interest. An example of the first kind would be the mechanization of the *Index Medicus*; of

the second, the creation of the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections.

Another limit upon program activity has been set by the high cost of technological development. It is not unusual for industry to spend many millions of dollars on the development of a single product, and the Council could not hope to emulate several well-known commercial ventures of the recent past involving the multi-million dollar development of information storage-and-retrieval systems and copying devices. By the same token, if government and industry are energetically supporting developments in a field (such as telefacsimile or machine translation) for their own purposes, the Council's intervention would be unlikely to affect final solutions and it should refrain.

Many a useful activity, launched with the assistance of a grant, has continued successfully. In the case of activities which are intended to continue, the initial decision to provide assistance must, in consequence, take into consideration the degree of brightness of the prospects of subsequent self or other support.

While the Council's program is not subject to any geographical limitations, yet it has made few grants abroad. The fact is, of course, that in many foreign countries (as also in the United States) the primary need of libraries is for means with which to adopt recognized solutions to their problems rather than for the development of new ones.

A final limiting factor upon the Council's program has been simple barrenness of invention. It is often easy to identify a problem but difficult to formulate a program to solve it. Pilferage, for example, is a problem common to many libraries but proposals for its solution are uncommon.

Ten years of assistance toward the solution of the problems of libraries

The projects supported by the Council over the past decade are listed by topic in the Appendix, together with the titles of the publications that reported the results. The list calls attention to the large number of elements on which library work is dependent, each one of which demands its share of attention and improvement. There is, in other words, no single central problem of library work, and no single solution.

Instead, advancement in the work as a whole results from improvement in details that may be as disparate as education for librarianship, the durability of catalog cards, or the organization of the book-trade in a country half around the world.

The list in the Appendix also exemplifies the successive steps that an attack upon a problem may require. These may include exploratory meetings, feasibility studies, mutually supporting grants or contracts, travel grants to widen the area of involvement and participation, and follow-up measures to publicize or implement findings or recommendations.

From the longer list in the Appendix the following selection furnishes examples of projects under a number of topics of interest, together with citations to the issues of the Council's annual reports in which they were described.

American library laws. After a lapse of more than twenty years the American Library Association brought out under the editorship of Dr. Alex Ladenson a new 1,559-page edition of *American Library Laws* (1964), providing at the same time for self-supporting updating of the compilation (*VII: 32; IX: 38-39**). The first supplement has since appeared.

Archives. The survey by Dr. Ernst Posner, sponsored by the Society of American Archivists, resulting in the book *American State Archives* (University of Chicago Press, 1964) not only set standards for long-term development but precipitated a number of immediate improvements (*VI: 36-7; IX: 11, 39, 48-51*).

An Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives met in Washington in 1966 under the auspices of the U. S. National Archives to consider and to adopt a continuing program to promote freedom of access to archival collections (*IX: 29; X: 46*).

Automation in libraries. In an early example of automation in a university library the University of California at San Diego in 1962-3 developed a computer program for controlling its record of serial acquisitions (*VII: 15-16; VIII: 17-18*).

*Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports; in this case to the 7th Annual Report, page 32 and the 9th Annual Report, pages 38-39.

In 1960-1 the Chicago Undergraduate Division of the University of Illinois, with a team from the General Electric Company, made a full-scale study of its operations resulting in the report *Advanced Data Processing in the University Library* (1962) (*V*: 29; *VI*: 33).

By 1960 it had become clear that automation, to be successful even within a single library, must take the form of a system, not of unrelated applications. By the same token, because of the bibliographical relationships between the Library of Congress and other libraries, the automation of its procedures would have, nation-wide, even wider implications. In the light of these premises a team of eminent experts (known from its chairman, Dr. Gilbert W. King, as the King Committee) made a careful study of the Library resulting in the report *Automation and the Library of Congress* (1963) (*V*: 29; *VIII*: 7, 41).

The King report provided guidelines for extending automation within the Library of Congress, but it was desirable that certain aspects should be hastened to promote the development of a national system in which other libraries could take part. The first of these was the creation of a standard for conversion of bibliographic (especially cataloging) data information to machine-readable form. Under the sponsorship of Inforonics, Inc., Mr. Lawrence F. Buckland prepared the report *The Recording of Library of Congress Bibliographical Data in Machine Form* (1964) (*VIII*: 43-44; *IX*: 9).

Book selection. In March 1964 the American Library Association commenced the publication of *Choice*, a monthly book-selection journal at the college level, currently publishing more than 5,000 book reviews per annum contributed by more than 2,000 specialists (*III*: 25-6; *IV*: 15; *VI*: 16; *VIII*: 19-20).

To complement the current service provided by *Choice*, the Association is publishing a basic list of 53,000 *Books for College Libraries* prepared by the library of the University of California at San Diego (*X*: 44).

To improve the quality of legal education through the strengthening of law school libraries, the Association of American Law Schools has undertaken the preparation, under the editorship of Dr. Miles O. Price, of a series of

lists of books in various legal subjects, describing altogether an "optimum" collection of about 200,000 volumes (*VIII: 18-19*).

Cataloging. A major step toward the international standardization of cataloging was made in the International Conference on Cataloguing Principles, Paris 1961, sponsored by the International Federation of Library Associations (*II: 10-11; IV: 13, 23; VI: 12-13*).

Further progress was effected when the American Library Association's new cataloging code, deliberately deferred for the Paris Conference, became the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*, now in press (*VII: 16; VIII: 14-15; IX: 16; X: 38*).

"Cataloging-in-source" consists in the printing of cataloging information in the book to which it refers. A demonstration conducted by the Library of Congress in 1958-9 resulted in a report, *The Cataloging-in-Source Experiment* (1960), which convinced many of the feasibility as well as desirability of the proposal. But the Library reached a contrary conclusion (*IV: 24-25*).

Cooperative book-acquisition. A review of the first ten years of operation of the Farmington Plan, conducted by Robert Vosper and Robert L. Talmadge in 1957-9 under the sponsorship of the Association of Research Libraries led to the continuance and extension of this nation-wide plan for the acquisition of foreign publications of importance for research (*III: 30-31*).

A study of the status of arrangements for the procurement of foreign publications under the provisions of the Agricultural Trade Development Assistance Act of 1954 as amended ("Public Law 480"), sponsored by the American Council of Learned Societies (1959), contributed to the successful implementation of these provisions for the benefit of American libraries and their users (*IV: 16*).

The Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center, established in Taipei in 1964 by Dr. Robert L. Irick for the Association for Asian Studies, supports Chinese studies in the United States through a wide range of services in book procurement, bibliographic service and reprinting of out-of-print editions (*IX: 35*).

The Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying, established experimentally in the Library of Con-

gress in 1965, is expected to make possible the improved use of available resources for copying materials for research in foreign libraries and archives (*IX: 24*).

Cooperative processing centers. The Southwest Missouri Library Service Center, a cooperative book-processing center established in 1957 to serve (initially) 10 independent public libraries, "set a pattern, unique at the time of its inception" for such organizations. They have since become commonplace (*II: 18-19; III: 45; V: 18; VI: 16-17*).

Deterioration/preservation of library book-stock. Although the impermanence of paper had excited alarm among librarians and others for more than a century, the full extent of deterioration of library book-stock was for the first time exposed by the investigations of W. J. Barrow sponsored by the Virginia State Library (1957). At the same time he identified the principal causes of deterioration in such a manner as to enable him to take effective remedial measures. Some of these measures were directed to the preservation of the records of the past; others to the development of improved paper and other materials for the records of the future (*I: 21-22; III: 31-32*).

The W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, established in 1961 and devoted exclusively to investigations concerned with the longevity of library materials, has published reports of a succession of studies under the general title *Permanence/Durability of the Book* (*VI: 21-22; VII: 20-23; VIII: 29-32; IX: 31-32*).

Under the sponsorship of the Association of Research Libraries a national plan for the preservation of deteriorating research library materials has been prepared by Gordon R. Williams (1964) and awaits implementation (*V: 21-22; VI: 22-23; IX: 29-30*).

The Federal Library Committee. In spite of repeated recommendations going back at least to 1896, no attempt to establish a mechanism by which the libraries of the Federal government could collaborate for better service had ever proved successful, principally because of the divided authority resulting from the Constitutional separation of powers. But a study of Federal libraries conducted by Dr. Luther H. Evans and Dr. Harold Orlans under the sponsorship of the Brookings Institution (1959-1963) paved the way to the

establishment in 1965 of the government-wide Federal Library Committee (*III*: 40-41; *VIII*: 44-45; *IX*: 12-13, 45-46).

The future of library work. Increasingly since Dr. Vannevar Bush's imaginative projection in July 1945 of the effects of "cheap complex devices of great reliability" on the information-using habits of intellectual workers ("As We May Think," *Atlantic Monthly* 176:101-8), questions have multiplied as to the probable effects of electronic and other devices on library work and the directions which planning and research should consequently take. In 1961-3, from a study of concepts and problems of libraries of the future conducted by Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc., a team headed by Dr. J. C. R. Lickliger developed in a series of reports and in a book (*Libraries of the Future*, 1965) the outlines and requirements for a "procognitive" information system resting on a man-machine "symbiosis." Meanwhile, to demonstrate some of the actual, if small, progress that had been made toward this future, exhibits of libraries with automated features were arranged by the American Library Association at the world fairs at Seattle, 1962 and New York, 1964-5 (*V*: 27; *VI*: 8-11; *VIII*: 38-41, 47-48; *IX*: 8).

Guides to resources. Prepared by Dr. Richard W. Hale, Jr., under the sponsorship of the American Historical Association, the *Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials in the United States and Canada* (1961) records the holdings of these important source materials in approximately three hundred North American libraries (*II*: 19-20; *VI*: 14).

The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections was established at the Library of Congress in 1958 and has since 1964 been continued with Congressional appropriations. Originally conceived as a card catalog, it was found possible to publish the record as a self-supporting operation. Four volumes have been issued, and with the fifth, in press, 16,397 collections in 492 repositories will have been described (*III*: 19-21; *VI*: 13-14; *VII*: 8-9; *VIII*: 9-12; *IX*: 24-25).

The third edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada* (1965), sponsored by a Joint Committee widely representative of library and scholarly interest, records in five folio volumes the holdings

of 156,499 different serial publications in 956 libraries (*III: 21-23; X: 35-37*).

High-density photostorage. The Verac, constructed by the AVCO Corporation, 1958-1961, could store a million pages in reduced facsimile in a cubic foot of space and could find and display or reenlarge any one of them in seconds. It demonstrated the engineering feasibility of high-density photostorage; in economic terms, however, it was a failure. But its lesson—to avoid mechanization so costly that it nullifies the savings from the micro-reduction—has been heeded in subsequent developments (*III: 34-35; IV: 28-30; VI: 25-28*).

Insurance. Libraries, prior to 1963, were categorized for insurance purposes with public buildings generally, including city halls and jails. A study of the situation sponsored by the American Library Association produced a manual, *Protecting the Library and its Resources* (Chicago, 1963), and resulted in the development and availability of a separate and improved policy for libraries (*V: 21; VII: 29-31; VIII: 33-34*).

Library technology. The Library Technology Project (Program) of the American Library Association, co-sponsored by the Special Libraries Association, has conducted since 1958 an extensive program of information, testing, standardization and development for library supplies, equipment and systems. In addition to columns in the library journals and a loose-leaf reporting service, it has issued numerous separate reports (*e.g.*, on copying equipment and book-charging systems) and manuals (*e.g.*, on insurance and catalog card reproduction). It has developed standards (*e.g.*, for library binding), improved library supplies (*e.g.*, catalog cards and pamphlet boxes) and equipment (*e.g.*, a labeling machine) (*III: 38-39; IV: 20-21; V: 27-28; VI: 34-36; VII: 38-39; VIII: 33-36; IX: 42-44*).

Library buildings. Dr. Keyes D. Metcalf's book, *Planning Academic and Research Library Buildings* (1965), was written in a project co-sponsored by the American Library Association and the Association of Research Libraries, which also made possible a significant reduction in the price of copies in order to encourage distribution (*IV: 20; X: 53-54*).

Machine-aided indexing. In an experiment conducted in 1959-62 by the Thompson Ramo Wooldridge Corporation under the direction of Dr. Don R. Swanson, a computer-aided search was able to identify 86% of the "source documents" as contrasted with 38% recovered without such assistance (*III: 26-28; IV: 23-24; V: 15; VII: 54*).

A method of searching statute law by computer was demonstrated by the University of Pittsburgh in 1960-1963 under the direction of Mr. John F. Harty (*V:15-16; VII: 12*).

A method of searching case law by computer was the subject of an investigation commenced in 1963 under the sponsorship of the American Bar Foundation (*VII: 13; VIII: 16-17*).

Mechanization of bibliographic compilation. The initial mechanization by which the National Library of Medicine's *Current List of Medical Literature* was converted in 1961 to the *Index Medicus* prepared for the important computer-based development (Medlars) that followed (*V:30; VII: 9-10*).

Microtext. The National Microfilm Association's *Guide to Microreproduction Equipment*, of which the first edition (1959) was subsidized, is now self-supporting and in its third edition, 1965 (*III: 37*).

Wildlife Disease, a quarterly publication originally on microcards, later on filmcards, 1959- demonstrated the feasibility of publishing a scientific journal in microform (*III: 33-34; VI: 28*).

Studies at the Battelle Memorial Institute, 1961-2, identified important factors affecting satisfaction in the reading of microtext, including the especial importance of high resolution, and demonstrating that under proper conditions microreproductions can be even more readable than the originals (*V: 24-25; VI: 24*).

A study by Dr. Wesley Simonton (1960-61) sponsored by the Association of Research Libraries, led to an improved standard for cataloging the microforms (*IV: 15; V: 31*). This opened the way to other developments, including the establishment in 1965 at the Library of Congress of the long-needed National Register of Microform Masters (*IX: 23-24*).

Permanent/durable book-paper and catalog card stock. W. J. Barrow's studies of the deterioration of library

book-stock left little doubt that the principal cause lay in manufacturing processes rather than in polluted atmosphere (the traditional culprit) and was not necessarily related to a particular kind of raw material. In a second study sponsored by the Virginia State Library, 1958-1960, he sought to obviate this cause at a cost that would avoid pricing the resultant paper out of the market. In this double objective he was successful. Today a number of papers of good and even of excellent prospects of permanence and durability are available in the medium price range (*III*: 31-32; *IV*: 26-29).

The capability of withstanding hard usage over a long period is especially necessary for catalog cards, but until 1960-61, when W. J. Barrow studied the subject under the sponsorship of the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association, libraries had no way of assuring such capability. Cards meeting the Barrow specifications for permanence/durability are now commercially available at prices in some cases even lower than libraries were previously paying (*V*: 17; *VI*: 20).

Photocopying of copyrighted materials. The "Single Copy Statement," developed by the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying with the assistance of counsel, was adopted in 1960-61 by four principal national library associations. The Statement asserts the traditional practice of libraries in furnishing copies of materials in their collections (*III*: 38; *V*: 32; *VII*: 53; *VIII*: 37).

Regional surveys. It has been frequently found that a comparatively inexpensive survey may prove disproportionately fruitful of good results, and this has been the Council's experience with a number of the regional surveys of the possibilities of improved library resources or services which it has supported in Arkansas, California, Colorado, Maine, New York, Ohio, Rhode Island and Canada (*IV*: 19-20; *VI*: 37-40; *VII*: 19-20, 32, 35-36; *VIII*: 46-49; *X*: 60).

School libraries. The American Association of School Libraries commenced in 1961-2 a campaign for the implementation of the School Library Standards of 1960 with such success that it obtained additional support in more than tenfold measure (*V*: 27; *VII*: 36).

Small libraries. The Small Libraries Project sponsored by the American Library Association prepared in 1962-3 a series of 16 manuals in pamphlet form with accompanying material for the use of libraries in communities of 10,000 or less population; 9,400 sets of these were distributed through state and provincial library agencies in the United States and Canada. In a subsequent project sponsored by the Drexel Institute of Technology Mr. Donald D. Dennis prepared a manual of work simplification for small libraries, 10,000 copies of which were similarly distributed through state agencies (*V*: 26-27; *VII*: 33-34; *IX*: 40-41).

Statistics. Long-needed standards for assuring the consistency and compatibility of library statistics were developed by Mr. Joel Williams in a cooperative effort involving the American Library Association, American Standards Association, Special Libraries Association and U. S. Office of Education, and resulted in the publication of *Library Statistics: A Handbook of Standards and Terminology* (1966) (*VII*: 31-32; *IX*: 39-40; *X*: 57-58).

Storage space. In *Patterns in the Use of Books in Large Research Libraries* (1961) the University of Chicago Library demonstrated a method of predicting the future use of books so as to make it possible to assign storage space on a use-expectancy basis (*III*: 32-33; *V*: 31-32).

In *Yale's Selective Retirement Program* (1963) the Yale University Library described its method for meeting the space problem through consignment of books to compact storage (*III*: 32-33; *VIII*: 28-29).

Subject-classification for law books. Because law alone has remained outside the Library of Congress classification scheme, law libraries lack the benefits of a centrally maintained and assigned classification such as is available in other subjects. But in an effort commencing in 1958 the Library of Congress has extended its scheme to Anglo-American law and is expected soon to begin to apply it so that the results will be available to law libraries generally (*III*: 23-25; *VI*: 18-19; *IX*: 16-18).

Telefacsimile. The demonstration of closed-circuit TV between libraries at the University of Virginia in 1957-8 identified some of the problems. A demonstration in 1966 involving Reno and Las Vegas, Nevada, and Davis, Cali-

fornia, showed progress in some particulars since the earlier date with further improvement still to be sought (*I*: 22-3; *IV*: 18; *V*: 25; *VI*: 31-32; *IX*: 36-37).

Information Storage and Retrieval

The ultimate concern of libraries is of course with the storage and retrieval of information. But to say this is greatly to oversimplify. Information is not only inseparable from the message by which it is conveyed to the senses of the recipient, but the message in its turn is inseparable from some physical medium in which it is stored or transmitted. Thus, information may be obtained from a word. The word, which is the message, may be perceived through the eyes, through the ears, or through the fingertips. It may be recorded in print, in magnetic spots or in raised type.

In addition, information is subjective, and is difficult to characterize adequately. But much may be learned about the information from the characteristics of the message (whether it is a novel, a song or a geographic representation), and from the characteristics of the recording medium (whether a book, or an acoustical recording, a map or a globe). Still other characteristics of the message and of the recording medium serve to characterize the information, such as the name of the maker, the size, language, date of production.

For all these reasons libraries ordinarily give as much attention (if not more) to the characteristics of the message and of the recording medium as to the contained information. Even when attention is given to information, it is related to the information in particular messages or records.

Such a system assumes that access to information is effected indirectly through the storage and retrieval of records, the objective of which is to enable an inquirer to examine the recorded messages and to gain information therefrom in his own way. Any improvement in the storage and retrieval of records will thus improve access to information.

Improvement in the storage and retrieval of records can be sought along at least three avenues. One of these is the improvement of the techniques by which records are characterized and described; in other words, by improvements in cataloging. Another is improvement in the apparatus for con-

sulting the catalog. Still a third consists of improved physical access to the records themselves. The Council has sought improvement of the information storage and retrieval capabilities of libraries along each of these avenues.

Storage. The generally best vehicles for information hitherto developed are still printed books. But books may be unsuitable because of cost, bulk, impermanence or other reasons. Alternatives to the book form which have been suggested or tried include microfilm and the other products of microphotography, punched cards, computer tape and video (television) tape.

Of these alternatives the one from which library work has gained and seems likely to gain most is microphotography. None of the systems to which the others belong seems likely, except under very special circumstances, to be able to justify the much higher cost. For example, while results may justify entering bibliographic citations into computer memory, they may rarely be expected to justify entering the full text of books, periodicals, etc.

Microforms, however, have a number of advantages for information storage. They can reproduce original documents inexpensively yet with a high degree of accuracy and expectation of longevity as well; they can effect significant economies of storage space and in costs of binding; their uniform format is conducive to efficient storage and ease of handling; it is often easier to maintain the integrity of a collection of microforms than of originals; the transparent microforms lend themselves readily to further processing such as the automatic production of re-enlargements when and as needed, as well as the processing required for facsimile transmission which is inefficient to perform with books.

These capabilities have gained wide acceptance for the microforms in libraries as substitutes for costly, unprocurable, non-circulating or deteriorating originals. In addition, the per page cost of microforms is such that for small editions they can compete successfully with full-scale publications and are preferred by a number of issuing agencies, *e.g.*, for maintaining depository collections of technical reports.

Meanwhile, over the past 15 years an almost continuous succession of devices has attempted to exploit the capabilities of photography for storage and retrieval of information by

combining a microphotographic store with a mechanism for selection and display. The milestones along this road of development bear such names as the Rapid Selector (1953), Minicard (1956), Filmorex (1957), FLIP (Film Library Instantaneous Presentation, 1958), Verac (1960), Media (1962), File-Search (1963), CRIS (Command Retrieval Information System, 1963), Miracode (1963), Walnut (1963), RADIC (Retrieval and Display of Information Chips, 1964), CARD (Compact Automatic Retrieval Device, 1964), Microvue (1965). In some of these (*e.g.*, Verac, Walnut) an internal store in the retrieval device had a capacity of up to a million page-images from which a desired image could be found and displayed within seconds. In others (*e.g.*, Minicard, Miracode) the store was of unlimited capacity but external and not so rapidly consultable. The development costs of these devices reach in some cases many millions of dollars, and many of them represented very considerable achievement in engineering terms. But, though a few of them have found specialized applications, none has received general acceptance for library work or been able to compete successfully with the traditional methods of information storage.

Why is this? Although various reasons, such as inability to provide random access or the difficulty of up-dating, account for the failure of individual devices to qualify, a principal general reason has been that the per-page cost of the microforms when combined with other costs and constraints accompanying their use, disables them from competing successfully, except in special circumstances, *e.g.*, in high-rent areas, with full scale publications in editions of normal size.

It may be conjectured, in consequence, that if their per-page cost could be significantly reduced, the microforms might make a dramatically increased contribution to the self-sufficiency of libraries.

Such an expectation argues from historical analogy. Before the invention of printing, the cost of books was so high that few libraries could afford to possess more than a few hundred, and local self-sufficiency was out of the question. Printing from movable types changed this situation overnight. Thousands of editions in the next few decades made it possible for libraries to acquire at comparatively small expense what previously had to be sought through the length

and breadth of Europe. Even today the contributions of Gutenberg's invention to local self-sufficiency continue to multiply through the expanding mass market of the paper-bound book.

The history of microphotography parallels that of printing. The use of photographs as substitutes for original documents is almost as old as photography itself, and with their decreasing cost this use overtook and displaced the hand transcript and the typescript. Photocopying was still expensive, however, when microfilm united a number of capabilities to greatly reduce cost, making possible a giant stride toward self-sufficiency. For while letterpress can provide only a transcript, the microforms furnish facsimiles. With their aid any library may assemble comparatively inexpensively in replica what no library, no matter how ancient or well endowed, can have entirely in the original.

However, to effect significant per-page costs reduction in the microforms is more easily said than done. At 10x reduction 100 pages can be accommodated in the area of one original page; at 100x reduction the same area will hold 10,000 pages. But the transition from 10x to 100x reduction is from a well understood and inexpensive technology to one that is demanding and expensive. Furthermore, the demands of the high-ratio technique are not satisfied with the production of a negative, but affect its reproduction into positives, and require compliance from the equipment used for viewing and for making re-enlargements. It is consequently not difficult to lose very quickly, in the increased cost of the technology, the theoretical advantages of the higher-reduction ratio.

Recently, however, there has been a renewed interest in the potentialities of high-reduction microfacsimile on the part of commercial organizations which are also aware of the perils. Because the principal markets expected by these companies are a long way from libraries, the Council during the past year commissioned a study, further described in Chapter II, to identify and measure some of the factors affecting the feasibility of high-density photo-storage in libraries.

Retrieval. The information retrieval apparatus used by libraries is not limited to a single instrument but is composed of many devices. Some of these are purchased ready-made

from publishers; others are constructed locally. In the first category are published catalogs, bibliographies, indexes and abstracting services, from a few hundred to many thousands in number, which are only indirectly related to the library's collection but without which its retrieval capabilities would be very poor indeed. In the second category are the library's own catalogs of its own collections on the shelves, and sundry special locally-constructed indexes and catalogs.

It is sometimes suggested that research would be facilitated by consolidation of the retrieval apparatus into a single mechanism. Even were this desirable, it would be infeasible. It would be possible but not advantageous to consolidate the catalog of a general book collection with an index to the journal literature of biology.

It is better, in consequence, to direct separate efforts for improvement of the retrieval apparatus to the locally-constructed and to the purchased portions. This is the course that the Council has pursued. While it has assisted the improvement of published bibliographical services which contribute indirectly to the organization of the collections of individual libraries, it has also sought means for improving the effectiveness of individual library catalogs, not only through improved cataloging, but also through improved methods for exploiting the results of cataloging.

It has long been the Council's conviction that the significant automation of library operations is dependent upon the inexpensive availability of bibliographic (i.e., cataloging) information of adequate and standard quality in accepted machine-readable form. Consequently, over the past six years the Council has supported a series of projects constituting a methodical approach to the automation of those library operations which have a base in the cataloging record. Among these are book-searching, ordering and accessioning, cataloging, shelf-listing, preparation for the shelves, book-charging, compilation of bibliographies and lists.

In Project MARC, discussed in Chapter I, there is described a pilot project for the distribution of cataloging information in machine-readable form. The availability of such information may be expected, at an initial stage, to assist libraries to improve their bibliography-based procedures. At a later stage it may be expected to promote the development

of links between the catalogs of the libraries of the country with a corresponding improvement of the retrieval capability of each.

The Council is simultaneously pursuing this objective from other directions also—from the point of view of the filing problem; from that of the renovation of an important but deteriorated card catalog; with respect to conversion of bibliographic information to machine-readable form by both manual and automatic techniques; and with respect to the possibilities of mechanization of the National Union Catalog. These approaches are also described in Chapter I.

The Eleventh Year

The Council's decade of existence has been one of increasing public concern with library problems and of increasing acceptance of responsibility for library support by the Federal and state governments.

As mentioned above, the date of the Council's establishment by a resolution of the Ford Foundation Trustees coincided with the approval of the Library Services Act of 1956. This Act authorized an annual appropriation of \$7.5 million for ten years, to be matched by the states, for extending library service to rural areas. Eight years later the Act was broadened, as the Library Services and Construction Act of 1964, to eliminate the restriction to rural areas, to include construction as well as service, and to increase the size of the authorized appropriation six times.

In 1956 the "information explosion" was already the subject of wide comment. Ten years later the phrase is still in common use, while the intensity of the "explosion" has if anything been emphasized by the very measures taken to control it but which also reveal its extent. With respect to scientific and technical information, the arrangements for dissemination came under sharp scrutiny as the result of the surprise caused in 1957 by Sputnik I. Much attention has subsequently been given by agencies of the Federal government, by professional associations, and others to improvement of these arrangements. One manifestation of this increased attention has been in the number of proposals for nation-wide communication networks for the exchange of information.

In 1956 the Council was the only organization committed to a program of research and development for the solution of library problems. Ten years later a different situation prevails. Several university-associated organizations have come into being specifically for the conduct of research in library problems, such as the Library Research Center of the University of Illinois (1961) and the Institute of Library Research of the University of California (1965), while many other agencies, both public and private, stand ready to undertake such research under grant or contract. Meanwhile, new sources of funds have become available for the support of research in library problems. The two most important of these result from Federal legislation of the past year. The Higher Education Act of 1965 authorizes grants for training and for research and demonstration in librarianship at the rate of \$15 million a year for three years. The Medical Library Assistance Act of 1965 similarly authorizes grants for research and development in medical library science at the rate of \$3 million a year for five years.

At the opening of its eleventh year the Council finds that it has participated in the identification of numerous important targets for attack; that it has assisted in attacks on many of them; and that a gratifying number of these have succeeded even though many problems still await solution. Meanwhile the entry of other agencies and the bringing of large resources to the work serve to corroborate the number, the difficulty, and also the importance of the problems in this field. With the assistance which these new resources will bring much progress in the solution of the problems of libraries may be looked for in the next few years.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

The Year Ending June 30, 1966

I. BIBLIOGRAPHIC APPARATUS AND TECHNIQUES

(The ultimate objective of library work is to put into the hands of a reader a book or other suitable record meeting his need. The devices and techniques by which an appropriate book is identified and its location is made known are those of bibliography.)

Projects Completed

Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada. The need for a new edition of the *Union List of Serials* was alluded to in the Council's first annual report. The *List* has been mentioned a number of times since the Council began its support of the new edition, beginning with a grant for a meeting of the Joint Committee on the *Union List of Serials* held in the Library of Congress November 3-4, 1958.¹ This year the project was completed; the work and a final report were published.

The first edition of the *Union List of Serials* was published in 1927 by the H. W. Wilson Company in cooperation with the American Library Association. (So important was the work regarded by the library world that 41 libraries each subscribed \$900 toward its cost—a very large sum for those days.) In the book's 1,580 pages were title entries for 75,000 magazines, bulletins and other publications (excluding newspapers) published in successive issues, and holdings of these publications were listed for 225 major North American libraries. A second edition, again published by the H. W. Wilson Company, followed in 1943. Its 3,065 pages listed 115,000 serial titles and the holdings of these in 650 libraries. Each edition was followed by two supplements, the last of which appeared in 1953.

The end of World War II found the library world already planning for a third edition of the *Union List*, and the Joint Committee on the *Union List of Serials*, which eventually came to represent 13 libraries and other learned bodies, was formed at that time. The infeasibility of a succession of editions, each almost double the size of its predecessor, was

¹ I: 8; III: 21-23; V: 11; VIII: 12-13.

recognized, What was the alternative? With assistance from the Rockefeller Foundation the Committee projected in 1957 *A Permanent Program for the Union List of Serials*, employing a punched card technique. This program, requiring an estimated \$2.7 million for initial implementation, was presented to the Council, but when funds were not found for it, a new plan was developed. This proposed that a third edition of the *Union List* should bring the record down through 1949, but that dependence for information regarding publications commenced after that date should be placed upon the monthly publication, *New Serial Titles*, established by the Library of Congress in 1951 and already constituting in effect a current supplement to the *Union List*. The new proposal was presented to the Council in March 1959 and was underwritten two months later by a grant for the preparation of a third edition.

The compilation of the new work was carried out under a contract between the Joint Committee and the Library of Congress.² In order to take advantage of the variable-aperture camera developed for the reproduction of the British Museum's catalog, copy preparation and printing were performed in England, and because the book must expect long years of hard usage, an especially manufactured paper with very low acidity and good folding and tear resistance was used. Again the H. W. Wilson Company is the publisher.

The new edition of the *Union List of Serials* comprises five folio-size volumes and totals 4,649 pages, containing entries for 156,499 serial titles held among 956 North American libraries.³ The increase in the number of titles reflects the active efforts on the part of research libraries to acquire older publications, the increased coverage of the new edition, and the proliferation of publication. Some half million serial titles have appeared since the early 18th century. Some 8,000 new titles, it is estimated, appear each year. As no library

² Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc.: *Final report . . . on the project . . . for the publication of a third edition of the Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada*. Submitted by Howard Rowelstad, Chairman. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1966. 52 p.

³ *Union list of serials in libraries of the United States of America and Canada*. Third edition. Edited by Edna Titus Brown under the sponsorship of the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials with the cooperation of the Library of Congress. Funded by a grant from the Council on Library Resources, Inc. New York. The H. W. Wilson Company, 1965. 5 vols., 4,649 p.

has ever been able to assemble even half of the titles in existence, the *Union List of Serials* with its record of library holdings is a finding aid indispensable to even the largest library.

Having now effected the first part of its plan for putting the record of serial holdings in American libraries on a permanent footing, the Joint Committee has moved to the second. In the closing days of the last fiscal year the Council authorized a new grant to enable the Committee to review the suitability of *New Serial Titles* as the continuing supplement to the third edition of the *Union List of Serials*.

Pre-1965 Files of the National Union Catalog. Some 500 American research libraries currently report their holdings of books to the National Union Catalog at the Library of Congress. The record for imprints of 1956 and later is published but the pre-1956 record remains in card form, available to the inquirer only at the Library of Congress or upon application for specific information. The Subcommittee on the National Union Catalog of the American Library Association's Committee on Resources is understandably eager to get this unique record into print to increase its availability, and has for some time been exploring methods for accomplishing this. Were the Catalog available in a machine-readable form, this would not only facilitate publication (by permitting automatic preparation of printer's copy) but might serve other purposes as well. Consequently at the Subcommittee's request the Council commissioned the International Business Machines Corporation to undertake a pilot project for converting the Catalog's 12.5 million cards to a machine record suitable for computer processing.⁴

The study has been completed and a report rendered.⁵ This describes, step-by-step, a procedure for converting the contents of the Catalog to machine-readable form and estimates the cost at from 35.31 to 41.7 cents per title or from \$4.4 to \$5.2 million for the entire Catalog.

The expenditure of sums of this magnitude could not be justified by the sole use of the machine record in the publi-

⁴ IX: 25-26.

⁵ International Business Machines Corporation. Federal Systems Division: *Report of a pilot project for converting the pre-1952 National Union Catalog to a machine readable record; a study sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc.* Rockville, Md., 1965. 52, [15] p.

cation of the Catalog. The question remains for exploration whether other uses exist to justify it, *e.g.*, in catalog-conversion projects in individual libraries, in regional and local union catalogs and bibliographic centers, and the like.

Anglo-American Catalog Code. The editing of this important bibliographic standard, for which the Council made a final grant to the American Library Association two years ago,⁶ was brought to substantial completion in the year just past. It remains to print and publish the results, and this is expected to be accomplished during the present year.

Rules for Full Cataloging of Music. The Council has in several instances assisted the Music Library Association to be represented in meetings abroad concerned with the development of an international standard for cataloging music.⁷ At the meeting of the International Cataloging Code Commission of the International Association of Music Libraries in Dijon in June-July 1965 the Rules for Full Cataloging of Music, as revised by the American representative, were approved. They are to be published by C. F. Peters, Frankfurt, as the third volume of the *Code internationale de catalogage de musique*.

World Bibliography of Bibliographies. This compilation, though the work of one man, Dr. Theodore Besterman, the editor of *Voltaire*, is without doubt the most comprehensive of all guides to resources. Its first edition (1939-1940) was in two volumes and contained some 25,000 entries; the second, 1947-1949, three volumes, 63,776 entries; the third, 1955-1956, four volumes, 84,403 entries. The fourth edition, toward the compilation of which the Council made a small contribution,⁸ has now appeared; it is in five volumes and lists 117,187 titles in 50 languages under 15,829 headings.⁹

Planning a Book-Selection List for Latin American Universities. Because of the deficiency of appropriate book-selection aids as well as difficulties of book-procurement, a book-list which would assist in forming sound basic collections at the university level is very much needed in Latin America. With assistance from the Council, the Pan American Union convened a meeting in San José Purúa, Mexico, in June 1966

⁶ VIII: 14.

⁷ V: 65; VIII: 15; IX: 16.

⁸ VII: 18.

⁹ Theodore Besterman: *A world bibliography of bibliographies and of bibliographical catalogues, calendars, abstracts, digests, indexes and the like*. 4th edition. Lausanne: Societas Bibliographica, 1966. 5 vols.

to make plans for such a list. The meeting was attended by representatives of the Unión de Universidades de América Latina, the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, the Mexican Library Association, the University of Texas, and the Pan American Union.

The Documentation of Documentation. Mr. H. Allan Whatley's report of his survey of major indexing and abstracting services in the field of library work and documentation¹⁰ has now been published *in extenso*.¹¹

The Mechanization of Filing Rules. One of the many rules for filing into a library catalog requires that abbreviated words be filed as though spelled out; otherwise it would be necessary to seek a word not only under its full form but under every possible abbreviation of that form. Now, while a human filer can easily judge from the context whether the abbreviation "St." should file as "Saint" or "Street," a computer requires explicit instructions. Consequently, if catalogs are to be successfully automated in the near future there is some urgency in determining whether the complicated rules which govern manual filing can be adopted to machine processing, or whether they must be simplified. In connection with an inquiry into the possibility of producing the California List of books suitable for college libraries by automated methods, the Council commissioned a study of the filing problem from Inforonics, Inc.¹² A report has been rendered¹³ which concludes that while it appears quite feasible to develop a computer program for a majority of the filing rules employed by the Library of Congress, the "program would be neither simple nor short, but neither is the rule book on which it is based nor the body of bibliographic data on which it would operate." The report outlines a procedure for attaining the objective, and meanwhile emphasizes the urgency of action, for unless decisions are made in this matter there is little assurance that machine records now being created will be machine-sortable by the filing rules of a future standard.

¹⁰ IX: 28.

¹¹ H. Allan Whatley: *A survey of the major indexing and abstracting services for library science and documentation*. London: The Library Association, [1966]. 78 p. Condensed in *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* 19: 226-231, September-October 1965.

¹² IX: 15-16.

¹³ William R. Nugent: *The mechanization of the filing rules for the dictionary catalogs of the Library of Congress*. Maynard, Mass.: Inforonics, Inc., 1966. 32 p.

A Cataloger's Camera. The original Cataloger's Camera was intended to create catalog cards by a dry photographic process from many kinds of copy, and even to insert "added" (filing) entries photographically.¹⁴ It did not achieve its objective, and more recent devices using the name have been less ambitious. During the past year Mr. Hugh Hazelrigg of Indiana University has constructed a Cataloger's Camera for use in making catalogers' enlarged copies from the miniaturized entries contained in such publications as the *National Union Catalog*. This camera has been successful in its own right and has also stimulated other attempts.¹⁵

New Projects

Next Steps to Automation in Libraries. The Council's program with respect to library automation has been guided by the conviction that any meaningful automation in libraries is dependent upon the machine-handling of bibliographic records. These records (typically the product of cataloging or other kinds of bibliographic description) identify and describe books, periodicals and other library materials. Unless such records can be handled automatically it is of only minor importance for a library to be able to automate its business or other records.

From this conviction the Council has reasoned that three preconditions were necessary to the genuine progress of library automation. The first of these was typographical. If computers are to be able to handle bibliographical records, they must command print-out of sufficient typographic variety to avoid the mutilation that results when bibliographic information is printed in capital letters only. This precondition has now been met through the introduction of chain printers and mechanisms for computer-controlled photocomposition.¹⁶

A second precondition is related to the first. Assuming the possibility of computer print-out in adequate typographic variety, agreement is required as to the computer language to control this variety. The alternative to such agreement is wasteful duplication of effort. Accordingly, as soon as it was assured that variety could be obtained, the Council com-

¹⁴ II: 14-15; III: 28.

¹⁵ Mary Helen Stanger: *The cataloger's camera*. Bloomington: Indiana University Libraries, [1966]. 8 p., typescript.

¹⁶ VII: 9-11; VIII: 7-8.

missioned a study directed to developing a standard for transcribing bibliographic information to a computer-readable form which would be capable of responding to all foreseeable typographic and bibliographic needs. In other words, by using suitable computer programs it would be possible to print out in various ways the bibliographic information converted to machine-readable form in accordance with such a standard. The study was completed and a report rendered,¹⁷ and the development of a standard is proceeding.

A third precondition, related to the first two, is that, due to the high cost of transcribing bibliographic information into machine-readable form, such transcriptions should be available from a central source just as are the printed catalog cards which they replicate. For American libraries generally, this means the Library of Congress.

By autumn 1965 the Library of Congress had progressed sufficiently in its automation program to plan a pilot project for the distribution of cataloging information in machine-readable form known as MARC (MACHINE READABLE CATALOG). The immediate aim of the project is the development of procedures and programs to make possible the centralized preparation and distribution of data from which participating libraries can automatically produce catalog cards, book catalogs, reading lists and other materials based upon the bibliographic record, using local computer facilities. The larger aim is to assess the ultimate feasibility of a national communications network in which machine-readable data would be transmitted electrically from library to library. The Council is assisting the Library by defraying costs for two studies in connection with it. The first, the MARC Feasibility Study, will investigate the bibliographic, economic and technological aspects of the proposed service plans for a system. The second, Catalog Data Studies, is directed to the creation of specific programs and procedures required for the distribution projects.¹⁸ The Library will itself bear the cost of preparing and distributing

¹⁷ IX: 8-9.

¹⁸ Several reports have resulted: *Proceedings of the Third Conference on Machine-Readable Catalog Copy, Library of Congress, February 25, 1966*. Washington: Library of Congress, 1966. 30 p. *MARC Pilot Project report No. 1. Magnetic tape format of the machine readable catalog record*. Washington: Library of Congress, 1966. [11], 11 p. *MARC Pilot Project report No. 2. Progress report*. Washington: Library of Congress, April 1966. 11 p. *MARC Pilot Project report No. 3. Interim technical report describing the MARC Pilot System*. Washington: Library of Congress, 1966. 28 p.

the machine-readable data, planned to commence in the autumn of 1966. Initial hopes were exceeded when it was found possible to increase the number of participating libraries from 10 to 16 which were found to possess the required facilities.¹⁹

Costs of Conversion of Bibliographic Data to Machine-Readable Form. While the MARC project looks to the automation of future records of bibliographic information, libraries will need to extend automation to their existing records. It is important to ascertain the best ways of doing this including those involving least expense. Information of this kind, among other things, was expected from the National Union Catalog study described above. In addition, however, the Council has made a grant to Michigan State University to enable it to compare three methods for converting its shelf list of some 600,000 cards to machine-readable form with the initial purpose of establishing an automated book-charging system. The three methods of conversion to be studied are based upon the key punch, the perforated paper-tape typewriter, and the optical scanner.

Conversion by Optical Scanning. Ideally, it should be possible to convert written text to machine-readable form by a wholly automatic method. Optical scanning is such a method, but in order to take advantage of it the text to be converted must meet exacting requirements of typography and positioning. The Los Angeles County Public Library, which has led in the development of the book-form catalog as an improvement over the card catalog for certain applications, is seeking a better method for preparing these than the one currently used. The Council is assisting the Library to evaluate a procedure by which bibliographic records would be prepared from the beginning in a form suitable for optical scanning. These could then be converted automatically to machine-

¹⁹ The library of the Argonne National Laboratory, in Illinois; the Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta; Harvard University, Cambridge; Indiana University, Bloomington; the Montgomery County (Maryland) School System; the Nassau County (New York) Library System; the National Agricultural Library, Washington, D. C.; the Redstone Scientific Information Center, in Alabama; Rice University, Houston; the Institute of Library Research at the University of California, Los Angeles; the University of Chicago; the University of Florida, Gainesville; the University of Missouri, Columbia; the University of Toronto; the Washington State Library, Olympia; and Yale University, New Haven.

readable form and could then be processed by computer for many purposes, including the preparation of the improved book-form catalog which is an immediate objective.

Catalog Renovation. The public catalog of the New York Public Library is a card file dating from the 1890's. In June 1963 it contained 7.8 million cards and was growing at the rate of 2.4 million cards per decade. But, because of concentrated use by millions of readers over the years, the age of the cards (some more than 70 years old) and the poor quality of many of them, the catalog was even then worn out. Forty-six per cent of the total required attention and 30 per cent, amounting to 2.3 million cards, required immediate replacement. Most of the latter were so far gone that it was no longer possible even to photograph them successfully.

In consequence, the Library faces renovation costs in the millions of dollars, but it must at the same time prepare for an increase in the rate of use which has created the present situation. And what is true for the New York Public Library today will confront other libraries tomorrow.

Accordingly, the Council has assisted the Library to fund a study of the various methods for meeting the situation and to develop a plan for the presentation and maintenance of its catalogs for the future.

A New State Union Catalog. Until now, union catalogs have been created by interfiling and consolidating sets of cards representing the holdings of the participating institutions. While this method has proved serviceable, it is defective in a number of respects. In consequence, any new union catalog project must examine alternative techniques, including those making use of computers, before adopting one. Mississippi has at present no union catalog, but the Information Services Division of its Research and Development Center at Jackson is interested in developing one. The Council has made a small grant for a preliminary survey of applicable techniques and comparative costs.

Computer-Controlled Typographic Composition. The Council has made a grant to the National Bureau of Standards to design and run tests of computer-controlled photocomposition of various kinds of bibliographic records, to study the manner in which advanced systems of computer-controlled composition can be applied to library uses, and to recommend configuration of devices for this purpose.

Book-Selection Lists. Charles B. Shaw's *A List of Books for College Libraries* (1931; *Supplement*, 1940) demonstrated the need for and value of a book-selection list at the college library level. It was replaced in 1953 by Harvard's *Lamont Library Catalogue* and in 1959 by the card list prepared for the University of Michigan's Undergraduate Library; but each of these in turn has been outdated. It became apparent that not only was a new basic list needed, but provision for keeping it up to date.

Of the two, the second is the more difficult. A basic list can be provided at any time that the necessary subsidy can be found, but a current list must pay its own way. It seemed to the Council that desirably the first step was to assure if possible the existence of the current list. In consequence, the monthly journal *Choice: Books for College Libraries*, was established with the Council's assistance in March 1964 by the American Library Association's Association of College and Research Libraries.²⁰

Meanwhile an opportunity presented itself for publishing a new basic list. In preparation for the opening of three new campuses of the University of California, the library of its San Diego branch (one of the three) prepared with great care, including review by faculty members and librarians familiar with undergraduate needs, a list of approximately 51,000 monograph titles. This list was offered by the University to the American Library Association for publication. An early hope that the list (known as "the California List") might have been made the subject of a demonstration of automated bibliographic procedures²¹ was disappointed and it will be published by more conventional methods. In the cost of these the Council is assisting. Publication is scheduled for autumn 1966.

Book-Selection Lists — Legal Literature. Two years ago the Council made a grant to the Association of American Law Schools to prepare lists of recommended books on a number of topics for use in legal education.²² The work was found to be more exacting than anticipated, and during the past year the Council has made a supplemental grant.

²⁰ III: 25-26; IV: 15; VI: 16; VIII: 19-20.

²¹ IX: 9-10.

²² VIII: 18-19.

Library Work with Children — Sources of Information. The Council has provided assistance to Miss Anne Pellowski for the completion of a work which will attempt to bring together in one volume references to all important sources of printed information on the development of children's literature and libraries in all countries, to provide a balanced view of developments in the field and to indicate locations of material cited.

Cataloging Rules for Publications in Urdu, Pushto and Panjabi. The absence of established cataloging rules for materials in certain foreign languages has resulted in a lack of uniform cataloging, sometimes even within the same library, with consequent confusion for the investigator. A situation of this nature existed some years ago when the Council gave support to preparation of *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description*, by Dr. Nasser Sharify. That this work, published by the American Library Association in 1959, met a need was evidenced by a second printing two years later.²³

This year the Council made a grant to Columbia University for the development of a cataloging code for publication in the three languages noted above. Under the guidance of Dr. Maurice F. Tauber, Melvil Dewey Professor of Library Service at Columbia University, the project will be carried out by Mr. Abdus Subbuh Qasimi, a teaching assistant at the University.

Use of the Dewey Decimal Classification Abroad. In 1963 the Council contributed to the cost of a survey of the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification outside of the United States with especial attention to the needs of users for adaptations of the classification which might reflect more closely than do the unadapted tables the literature, history, religion and geography of their countries. The survey was sponsored by the American Library Association which designated a steering committee to supervise it. Two surveyors, Miss Sarah K. Vann and Miss Pauline A. Seeley, visited libraries and library groups in 21 countries especially in Africa and Asia, and a report has been issued.²⁴

²³ II: 11; III: 25; V: 16-17.

²⁴ Sarah K. Vann: *Field survey of the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) use abroad. Final report.* New York: [The Steering Committee] 1965. 214 p.

II. PHYSICAL ACCESS

(The bibliographical apparatus is merely a means to an end. Ultimately, the cited work—manuscript, book or periodical—must be seen and consulted, either in its original form or in some acceptable facsimile.)

Ease of Access to Archives. The contents of archives, as primary source material, make the stuff of history, essential not only to a nation's own scholars but to those of others also. With the hope of effecting the liberalization of rules governing the accessibility of archival material and in advancing cooperation among the world's archives, the National Archives of the United States invited the International Council on Archives to hold an Extraordinary Congress (so called because it was not one of the Council's regular quadrennial congresses) in Washington. The Council on Library Resources, which has a mandate to foster such accessibility,¹ made a grant to the National Archives Trust Fund Board in June 1965 to assist the meeting,² and when interest in the Congress called for a larger attendance than originally planned, made a supplemental grant six months later.

The sessions of the Congress, which were held May 9-14, 1966 in the International Conference Room of the U. S. Department of State, brought together 438 delegates and observers from 52 countries, the United Nations and Vatican City. At the close of its sessions the International Council reaffirmed its objective of facilitating the use of archives by making them widely known and easily accessible. The meeting also affirmed its belief in the principle of equal and easy access to archives by all researchers, regardless of nationality, and recommended that steps be taken to implement this principle. Among its other recommendations it urged that certain categories of documents be opened to consultation even sooner than the general time limits now permit.³

¹ The Ford Foundation: *Annual Report* 1956:27.

² IX: 29.

³ The official text of the resolutions will be published in *The American Archivist*, Unesco's *Bulletin for Libraries* and the International Council on Archives' *Archivum*. A summary of the Extraordinary Congress' daily sessions and of the resolutions appears in an appendix to the *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* (25: 267-275. May 26, 1966) prepared by Dorothy S. Eaton, John D. Knowlton, John McDonough, Russell M. Smith and Donald C. Holmes, George O. Kent, and Elizabeth E. Hamer.

THE EFFECT OF COLDER ROOM TEMPERATURES on books is being studied by David D. Roberson, left, and Mrs. Patricia C. Turner in these two recently installed rooms at the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. Temperatures and humidity are constant in both insulated rooms, with that of the left simulating a library reading room and that at the right a book storage area. The degree to which colder-than-usual temperatures increase the physical life of books is the question under study here.

Preservation of Library Materials—The W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. In 1961, as has been previously reported, the Council made it possible for Mr. William J. Barrow to design and equip a laboratory for the purpose of conducting investigations into the preservation of books and related library materials.⁴ The Laboratory, located in Richmond in fine space made available by the Virginia State Historical Society, is perhaps the only one in the world devoted wholly to independent research in this field.

The first inquiry conducted by Mr. Barrow with the Council's support sought to ascertain just what had happened to book paper in the United States in the period 1900-1949, and why. The results were published in 1959 by the Virginia State Library which had sponsored the investigation.⁵ During the past year the Laboratory has been pursuing these questions back into the previous century. It is ordinarily said that impermanence in paper became a problem when rag was displaced by wood as a principal raw material of paper about 1870. What are the facts? In the search for precise information

⁴ VI: 21-22, 23; VII: 20-23; VIII: 29-32; IX: 12, 31-32, 33-35.

⁵ W. J. Barrow: *Deterioration of book stock: causes and remedies.* Edited by Randolph W. Church. Richmond: The Virginia State Library, 1959.

which may have great practical value for the manufacture of paper or for the storage of books, the Laboratory has assembled a number of examples of papers for each decade from 1800 to 1899 and has been conducting careful tests. By the end of the year it had accumulated some very interesting findings, but publication of a report has been withheld pending the development of a test for distinguishing cotton fibers from flax, which was still an important raw material for paper in the early 19th century.

In 1963 the Laboratory reported the results of a preliminary study indicating that for each lowering of 20° C. in the heat-aging temperature it takes 7.5 times as long to reduce the strength of a book paper to a given value.⁶ These findings, extrapolated to normal storage temperatures, were immediately seized upon by the library world as assuring great improvement in the arrangements for book storage through lowered temperatures.⁷ However, much must still be learned about the performance and use of paper at low temperatures, and the Laboratory has been continuing its experiments. Because of the slowness of aging reactions at lower temperatures it has commissioned especially manufactured reactive papers which will age more rapidly at low temperatures than regular papers, and it has constructed special rooms for tests involving the withdrawal of books from low-temperature storage for use in reading rooms at higher temperatures.

During the past year also the Laboratory completed a search for a permanent/durable adhesive suitable for "perfect" book-binding for libraries.⁸ In this type of binding, familiar in telephone directories and paperback books, the leaves are held together by adhesive at the binding margin. Such a binding is preferable to some other types of library binding, but only if adequate performance of the adhesive can be assured. The adhesives ordinarily used often embrittle after a few years, allowing the books so bound to fall apart upon use. In spite of the lack of natural aging experience with such adhesives to furnish a yardstick with which to compare the results of accelerated aging in the laboratory, it was found possible to devise tests for this purpose and finally to com-

⁶ W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory: *Permanence/Durability of the book*. Richmond: 1963, p. 21.

⁷ See, e.g., Gordon Williams: The preservation of deteriorating materials. *Library Journal* 91:51-56, 189.94. January 1, 15, 1966. P. 53-54.

⁸ VII: 21-2; VIII: 30; IX: 33.

pound an adhesive with an estimated prospective life of not less than 450 years. A report has been published providing full experimental data.⁹

In addition, as described below, the Laboratory has conducted a program of tests and has designed and constructed testing equipment on behalf of the American Library Association's Library Technology Program for the purpose of developing performance standards for library binding.

During the past year the Council renewed its contract with Mr. Barrow for another two years.

Telefacsimile Between Libraries. Last year's report recorded a grant by the Council to the University of Nevada toward the costs of an experiment with an inexpensive method of telefacsimile, the Xerox Magnavox telecopier, which uses a telephone line for transmission and a telephone handset as part of the terminal equipment.¹⁰ The experiment, conducted last April and May, consisted of 80 hours of transmission between the Reno and Las Vegas campuses of the University (the Governor of Nevada released the use of his official telephone line for the experiment during evening hours) and an equal amount of time between Reno and the Davis campus of the University of California. The librarians of the institutions involved conclude that if greater uniformity can be achieved, the quality of copies produced during the test suggests that the device has promise for library application where transmission costs are low.¹¹ They point out that the feasibility of telefacsimile for library applications has been limited by high transmission costs and poor quality of copies with inexpensive equipment and by the high cost of the high-speed, high-definition systems, and one of their purposes has been to stimulate library demand for lower cost and higher quality systems.

Meanwhile, the Council has made a small grant to the Institute of Library Research, University of California, to enable it to plan an experiment with telefacsimile in comparison with interlibrary loan.

⁹ W. J. Barrow. *Polyvinyl acetate (PVA) adhesives for use in library bookbinding*. Richmond, Va.: W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, 1965. 66 p.

¹⁰ IX: 36-37.

¹¹ David W. Heron and J. Richard Blanchard: Seven league boots for the scholar? Problems and prospects of library telefacsimile. *Library Journal* 91: 3601-3605, August 1966.

Microphotography at High Reduction. The Council has long hoped that the cost of dissemination and storage of library materials, especially seldom-used materials, could be significantly reduced through high-density storage obtainable by microphotography at high ratios of reduction (e.g., 100x or more). In all attempts up to this time, however, the savings resulting from high-density storage have been nullified by the costs of the equipment required to handle the microimages.¹² The Council has this year commissioned a new investigation from the Republic Aviation Division of the Fairchild Hiller Corporation. This study will seek to identify and estimate the effect of factors (size, contrast, optics, photosensitive materials, etc.) affecting the usefulness of microcopy at high reduction and develop a model for optimizing the product in any particular case. Film chips will be made demonstrating optimum use of high reductions up to 300, a laboratory model of a viewer will be constructed for evaluating such microimages under various conditions, and an engineering study will investigate the feasibility of procuring hard copy from the microimages.

A Filmcard Camera-Processor. Filmcards (sheet microfilm, also known as microfiches) constitute an accepted medium for the publication of technical reports and other literature where the number of needed copies is small although the number of pages involved may run into the millions. The Council has been interested to see developed a comparatively inexpensive device for making filmcards in a library environment. As a result, the Houston Fearless Corporation has constructed the prototype of a Film Camera-Processor which has been exhibited at the annual meeting of the National Microfilm Association and has since been placed for field testing at the Institute of Library Research at the University of California, Los Angeles.

The device is a step-and-repeat camera-processor, a feature of which is a copy-easel on which books or periodicals to be copied can be placed face up, open at a 90° angle. After exposure, the filmcard is automatically developed, fixed, washed, dried, and presented ready for use in about one minute. The filmcards are standard 4 by 6 inch (105 x 148.75 mm.) microfiches, and can contain a maximum of 60 microimages and a full-size title.

¹² V: 23; VI: 25-28.

Microcopying Equipment—An International Guide. In 1959 the Council assisted the National Microfilm Association to publish a guide to microfilm equipment available for purchase in the United States.¹³ This guide, which presented in standardized form data about the characteristics, performance and price of such equipment, proved so useful that the Association published revised editions in 1962 and 1965 and has provided an interim up-dating service as well.

This past year, the Council made a grant to the International Micrographic Congress for a complementary publication devoted to microfilm equipment available outside of the United States. The guide, which will have English text, is expected to be available sometime in 1966. The International Micrographic Congress includes member associations in Europe, Australia, and Japan, in addition to the National Microfilm Association.

Journal Publication in Microform. Last year brought to an end the Council's support (jointly with the National Science Foundation) of an experiment in publishing a scientific journal in microform, commenced in 1959 and renewed in 1962.¹⁴ Two reasons justified the publication of the microform journal *Wildlife Disease*¹⁵—the members of the Wildlife Disease Association were too few to support a letterpress journal; and their articles when submitted to other journals were excessively abridged. Microform made it possible for the Association to control the format, content and timing of publication without too much expense. As the form of publication, the 3 x 5-inch opaque microform (Microcard) was selected; each card reproduced 40 2-column pages of typewritten text especially prepared for reproduction (at 16-18 diameters reduction) in this form. Each of the 46 issues published during the life of the project was accompanied by a leaflet abstracting the published articles, and the abstracts were also reported to *Biological Abstracts*. Several times during the experiment the subscribers were furnished with the same material in both opaque and translucent form, but each time they preferred the opaque. Meanwhile, others discovered the value of micro-

¹³ III: 37. Hubbard W. Ballou: *Guide to microreproduction equipment*. Annapolis: National Microfilm Association, 1959. 438 p.

¹⁴ III: 33-34; VI: 28.

¹⁵ *Wildlife disease*. Washington, D. C., later Chicago, Ill.: Wildlife Disease Association, 1959-. Quarterly; published initially as Microcards, later as microfiches.

fiche, leading to its adoption as a standard for documentary dissemination, and in May 1965 *Wildlife Disease* conformed.

At the commencement of the project the Council provided the subscribers with a simple hand-reader. Most subscribers, it eventuated, being laboratory biologists, preferred to use low-power binocular microscopes, and this fact possibly accounted for the preference for the opaque form. In any case, the general problem of a satisfactory hand-reader for microform still remains to be solved. Nor was the problem of publication in color (important for pathological studies) satisfactorily dealt with.

Although the Association is now able to support a letterpress bulletin, it is continuing the microfiche series for long articles, articles for limited audiences, and extended bibliographies. At least one other journal in microform (*International Microfilm Journal of Legal Medicine*) is known to exist.

An Inexpensive Reader-Printer. A reader-printer is a device which can both project on a screen an enlarged image from microfilm or microfiche and also make an enlarged paper print (known as "hard copy") of the image. Late in 1963 the Council contracted with Documentation Incorporated for the manufacture for test purposes of seven reader-printers, a prototype of which had been developed by the company.¹⁶ The device, used for viewing microcopies and making enlarged paper prints of such microimages as are desired, was found to be susceptible of further refinement. The Council this past year made a further small grant for this purpose.

¹⁶ VIII: 24-25.

III. ADMINISTRATIVE ARRANGEMENTS

(A book becomes physically accessible when it reaches its place on the shelf; it acquires bibliographical accessibility when it is adequately cataloged. But to achieve these results and to put them at the service of an enquirer, still other elements are needed — the design and equipment of a building, the training and organization of staff, development of sources of financial support, etc. These and other administrative arrangements constitute a third principal category of activities of which library work is composed.)

Metcalf on Library Buildings. In 1959 the United States had already entered upon a period unequalled for its energetic construction of library buildings great and small — public libraries, college and university libraries, medical libraries, and rare book libraries. For two decades there had been animated discussion of the principles and practice of library building design and there had been both informal continuing study groups of prospective builders of libraries and more formal building institutes in which librarians and architects debated specific plans for days at a time. But nowhere were the results of these discussions sufficiently brought together, nowhere was there a distillation of principles and practice nor an adequate source of general guidance to the prospective owner, occupant or architect of a new library building.

There was, however, a potential source of such a compendium. As Librarian of Harvard, Mr. Keyes D. Metcalf had participated in the planning of a number of important library buildings. His retirement in 1955 freed him to pursue this work as a consultant to such an extent (he has participated in the planning of more than 250 library buildings on six continents) that it soon became inevitable that his experience and wisdom should be set down and given wider accessibility through the pages of a book. Accordingly, an arrangement was concluded whereby Mr. Metcalf undertook to prepare a work under the joint sponsorship of the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries of the American Library Association with assistance from an

advisory committee and financial assistance from the Council.¹ It was hoped that the latter would contribute toward keeping down the price of the eventual publication, so as to encourage a wide sale, both at home and overseas.

The resulting work, *Planning Academic and Research Library Buildings*, was published during the past year.² It is believed to be the first single publication designed to serve as a comprehensive text on the problems directly involved in the planning and construction of academic and other research library buildings. It is addressed equally to administrators, librarians and architects. It deals in specifics and contains numerous plans.

The Library Technology Project. Despite the services of its professional organizations, library work has been handicapped by insufficient information about equipment and supplies in daily use and about the comparative efficiency of routine methods of operation. There was no central source of information, no place where the librarian could turn to learn the relative merits of record players suitable for library use, or where sustained effort could be given to the devising of better book-charging systems. To fill this vacuum, the Council assisted the American Library Association to establish the Library Technology Project as a headquarters activity in 1959 and has continued to support it since then. The Project has proven its usefulness and has reached a point at which it is no longer wholly dependent upon the Council for support. In its current fiscal year 54 per cent of the operating funds and 21 per cent of the research funds are budgeted to derive from sources other than the Council.

Evolution has occurred in another respect also. As of September 1, 1965, LTP became the nucleus of the Association's newly established Office for Research and Development while retaining its own identity and continuing its regular activities.³ And as of July 1, 1966, in a change suggesting permanence, LTP has been designated Library Technology Program.

¹ IV: 20; VII: 28.

² Keyes D. Metcalf: *Planning academic and research library buildings. Sponsored by the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries under a grant by the Council on Library Resources.* New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, [1965]. 431 p.

³ Cf. Gladys T. Piez: Library Technology and RTSD—goals in common. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 10: 13-17, Winter 1966.

During the past year LTP continued to provide an information service on library supplies, equipment and systems, preparing monthly columns for the membership bulletins of the American Library Association and of the Special Library Association (which is represented on LTP's advisory committee). The loose-leaf subscription service *Library Technology Reports*, which since January 1965 provides information about products in much greater number and detail than was formerly possible, had gained 770 subscribers by the end of the year.

Early in 1964, LTP contracted with William R. Hawken for the preparation of a manual of documentary reproduction.⁴ This was completed during the past year, and publication will take place during the current year. Meanwhile, however, LTP has contracted with William R. Hawken Associates for a continuing program of testing and evaluation to keep the information in the manual up to date through the publication of supplements from time to time.

Mr. Hawken is the author of two previously published LTP reports — *Photocopying from Bound Volumes*, and *Enlarged Prints from Library Microforms*.

DATA ON ONE OF A SERIES OF MICROFICHE READERS in process of evaluation for the Library Technology Program is tabulated by William R. Hawken and research assistant Linda C. Muldoon.

In another study, LTP commissioned the Buyers Laboratory to test bracket-type steel book shelving available on the American market with a view to establishing performance standards for this equipment.

⁴ VIII: 35.

Care and Repair of Books. LTP also developed plans last year for a three-volume manual on the preservation and restoration of books and other library materials. As formulated by an advisory committee under the chairmanship of Mr. Harold Tribolet, Head of the Extra Bindery Department of R. R. Donnelley & Sons Company, Chicago, these plans call for one volume to be devoted to the care and repair of ordinary books, a second devoted to rare books, and a third devoted to the conservation of other types of material such as maps, prints, photographs, motion picture film and disk and tape recordings. The work will be addressed to the reader without specialized training and the emphasis is to be on practical techniques with detailed information and illustrations.

Book Typography for the Visually Handicapped. A study on this subject was completed and the results have been published.⁵ The study, conducted by Professor Jack Prince of the Institute for Research in Vision at Ohio State University, found that some common type faces, such as Baskerville, if sufficiently large, are more easily read by persons of limited vision than specially prepared type. It was also found important that the printed characters should have sharply defined edges free from blur and the paper should have high contrast and good opacity.

In collaboration with the Documentation Division of the Special Libraries Association, LTP has commissioned a survey which will provide concrete evidence of the progress of automation in American libraries by furnishing a census of functions performed and equipment used.

LTP has also continued its studies of charging systems, extending these to recently developed systems for imprinting with embossed cards (Demco) and for employing computers in the book-charging process (International Business Machines Corporation). An attempt to develop an improved book-charging system for college libraries was unsuccessful. An investigation has been initiated into the characteristics of catalog card cabinets. Some eighteen 15-tray cabinets, representing the entire American commercial market, will be tested for strength, finish, etc. The results will be published as a guide to purchasers, and will also be used to establish standards for these important articles of library furniture.

⁵Typography for the low vision reader. *Book Production* 41: 28-29, December 1965.

Standardization of Library Statistics. An outstanding characteristic of library statistics has been the incompatibility between those gathered by different libraries and in different countries. This has stemmed from lack of agreement on the definition of the most fundamental units — a book, a library, library use, reference service. In 1961 there were found to be 156 major recurring statistical surveys in the United States, but attempts to use them for comparative purposes were difficult or impossible.

Efforts to rectify this situation have been made from time to time over many years. In 1963 the American Library Association, Special Libraries Association, American Standards Association, Association of Research Libraries and U. S. Office of Education joined hands in sponsoring a study to develop standardized practices and terminology. The Council made a grant for the purpose which was supplemented by the National Science Foundation, and the National Library of Medicine provided work space.⁶ Mr. Joel Williams of the U. S. Office of Education was given a year's leave of absence to head the project. Its overall purpose was to lay the basis for the coordination of statistics in academic, public, school and special libraries at the national, regional, state and local levels, and the plans called for the development of a published handbook of definitions and standards and the convening of a national conference to promote their adoption.

The handbook was published in the spring of 1966 and the national conference was held shortly thereafter.⁷ The book contains no statistics, but seeks to standardize terms, definitions and concepts for statistics relating to the several types of libraries. The accomplishment has been widely acclaimed, and it would appear that a satisfactory solution has been brought to a long-felt problem.

Meanwhile, as a result of similar difficulties met by Unesco in its attempts to assemble library statistics for the countries of the world, and as a result of reports of the American accomplishment, the International Standards Organization had become interested in the possibility of erecting some standards

⁶ VII: 31-32; IX: 39-40.

⁷ *Library Statistics: A handbook of concepts, definitions, and terminology.* Prepared by the Staff of the Statistics Coordinating Project, Joel Williams, Director. Chicago: American Library Association, 1966. 160 p.

in this area.⁸ To take advantage of this situation the Council made a small grant to the American Standards Association to facilitate a meeting of representatives of Unesco, the International Standards Organization and the International Federation of Library Associations. The meeting was held in May 1966 with some immediate and more prospective accomplishments.⁹

Standardization in Library Work. Among the sectional committees of the American Standards Association (now the USA Standards Institute) is one for Standards in Library Work and Documentation. The work of this committee has been assisted in the past by complementary grants from the National Science Foundation and the Council on Library Resources.¹⁰ This year the Council again joined the Foundation in making a grant to the University of North Carolina—whose librarian, Mr. Jerrold Orne, is chairman of the Committee—to facilitate the work of the Committee's 15 subcommittees whose assignments range from computer input of bibliographic information to library bookbinding.

The Federal Library Committee. The establishment of the Federal Library Committee in March 1965, and its background, have been described in previous annual reports.¹¹ The Committee, whose purpose is to improve coordination and planning among Federal libraries and whose headquarters are in the Library of Congress, is composed of 12 permanent members who represent the three national libraries—Library of Congress, National Library of Medicine, and the National Agricultural Library—and the libraries of nine Executive departments—Commerce, Defense, Interior, Justice, Labor, Post Office, State, Treasury, and Health, Education and Welfare. The Committee also includes six members representing independent Federal agencies on a rotating basis. The Librarian of Congress, Mr. L. Quincy Mumford, is chairman of the Committee and Mr. Paul Howard, formerly Librarian of the Department of the Interior, is executive secretary.

⁸ Frank L. Schick: The international standardization of library statistics. *ALA Bulletin* 58: 1011-13, December 1964.

⁹ *Conference on library statistics. Report of a conference sponsored by the International Federation of Library Associations and the International Organization for Standardization . . . The Hague . . . 2d-7th May 1966.* [N.p.] 1966. 23 p.

¹⁰ VI: 34; VII: 39; VIII: 36.

¹¹ III: 40-41; VIII: 44-45; IX: 45-46.

The Committee has inventoried the issues confronting the Federal libraries as a group and has established task forces to work on such subjects as automation, acquisitions, standards of service, procurement, interlibrary loan, and recruitment of personnel. A project for early completion is the preparation of a compendium of laws and regulations relating to Federal libraries.

This past year the Council on Library Resources, which had previously made an initial grant to support a secretariat for the Committee, renewed the grant for a three-year period.

Archival Treatment of the Records of Academic Scientific Research. The records of scientific and technological research performed at the University of Illinois correspond in quantity to the importance and volume of the research itself. To assure the future accessibility and usefulness of these records their archival character requires to be recognized. A grant has been made to the University to enable its Archivist, Mr. Maynard Brichford, to prepare a manual of practice for the evaluation, processing and preservation of records of this kind.

A Survey of Systems of Public Libraries. The standards for public library service promulgated by the American Library Association in 1956 are contained in the publication, *Public Library Service: A Guide to Evaluation with Minimum Standards*. It is there stated that a minimum population base of 250,000 is needed to support adequate public library service, and it is accordingly recommended that smaller public libraries should unite in systems to achieve this base. During the decade that has passed since the publication of the standards, many libraries have followed the recommendation and today there are over 1,250 library systems, many of them extending beyond county lines or other boundaries of political jurisdiction. But as the multi-jurisdictional systems have grown, they have encountered difficulties; some have been threatened with the withdrawal of the larger and stronger member communities; others have found that the construction of the administrative center of the system has raised such questions as that of equality of service.

In view of the importance of the system concept to the development of public library service in this country, the Council has made a grant to the American Library Association to enable its Public Library Association to conduct a study of the operation of the systems. The study, expected to require

approximately 18 months, will assemble data on about one thousand library systems in the United States; from an analysis of the data, a series of case studies will be designed to identify typical strengths and weaknesses; and a comprehensive report, with recommendations, will be published.

Coordination of Resources — New York. In 1963 the Council and the Old Dominion Foundation made matching grants to enable a committee of New York librarians to conduct a survey of resources and of organization for reference and research in libraries in New York City.¹² The Board of Regents of the State of New York had adopted a plan for state-wide coordination of library and research resources, and studies to anticipate the effect of the plan were needed, especially in that area in which the greatest concentration of both resources and users is found. Out of the survey came a recommendation from which has resulted the establishment of the New York Metropolitan Reference and Research Library Agency, a non-profit organization whose purpose is "to improve reference and research library services in the New York metropolitan area by promoting and facilitating utilization of existing resources and developing additional resources."¹³ It is expected that the Agency will provide the basis for mobilizing the assistance of existing library organizations and for securing the funds necessary to sponsor and sustain a workable program of library cooperation.

The Council has made a one-year grant to enable the Agency to commence its work by reviewing previous proposals for library cooperation and to develop and initiate the implementation of a practical plan.

¹² VIII: 47.

¹³ *Prospects for library cooperation in New York City; planning for more effective utilization of reference and research resources.* New York: Nelson Associates, Incorporated, 1963. 135 p. Also: Report on New York Library Resources. *Special Libraries* 55: 106-107, February 1964.

IV. PLANNING

Library Service for a Community of Tomorrow. It is only rarely that city planning occurs otherwise than after the city; and for library services this is even more invariably the case. Consequently, when the Council was approached for a modest grant to study the possibilities of library service for a community that was still on the drafting boards, a welcome occasion was offered for seeing what could be devised when starting without fetters.

The community in question is Columbia. As planned, Columbia will consist of a town center and a grouping of villages with satellite neighborhoods occupying 22½ square miles in Howard County, Maryland, half way between Washington and Baltimore. By 1980, it is expected, Columbia's population will approximate 110,000 to 150,000 persons living in some 29,000 homes and other residential units. The question posed by Columbia's developers (Community Research and Development, Inc.), by the Trustees of the Howard County Library and by an advisory committee appointed by the Trustees and headed by Miss Nettie Taylor, the Maryland State Director of Library Extension, was what kind of library services should be planned for Columbia.

The question was submitted to a team headed by Mr. C. Walter Stone of the University of Pittsburgh. Mr. Stone, with three associates (Dr. Richard Darling, Dr. Harold Goldstein and Dr. Philip Lewis) submitted a report¹ proposing a library system that would go far beyond books and buildings to be part of a communications system involving a wide variety of telecommunication services, both audio and visual. These services would be available not only to inter-connected libraries and schools but also to homes and other community units. Some services would be free while others would be available on a fee or subscription basis. The communications system would be under the control of a board of directors, each of whom would represent a segment of the educational, cultural or economic community, and would be administered by a professional staff.

Some unusual consequences would result from the service thus planned. For example, both school and public library

¹ C. Walter Stone. *A library program for Columbia*. Pittsburgh, Pa. 1965. 49, 5 p.

service and staff would be under unified management with sharing of the facilities by both kinds of libraries at the village level. To quote the report, "In effect, the village library is neither a school library nor a public library, but a library of a new type, administered by a new agency, which can meet the needs of the entire village population, in school or out."

With reference to the various technological features proposed, the report observes that components have been tried and tested separately; in Columbia they would be integrated in a system.

The Council on National Library Associations. This organization, founded in 1942, provides a forum for discussions of common problems by representatives of some thirteen national organizations, but has no staff or income to carry out decisions. In spite of this, it is credited with some useful accomplishments, such as founding the emergency American Book Center and its continuing successor, the United States Book Exchange, launching an annual of library work and sponsorship of the committee for erecting standards with respect to the application of photography to library work and documentation. It is believed by many that the organization is needed and that it can be much more effective than it is, but the sources of effectiveness have proved elusive.² The Council has made a small grant to explore the matter.

The 1965 FID Congress. The International Federation for Documentation (ordinarily known by the initials of its name in French) traces its origin, in the last decade of the 19th century, to the efforts of two Belgian lawyers, Paul Otlet and Henri La Fontaine, to develop a world-wide scheme and organization for the coordination of bibliography. Until the past year, the Federation had never met in the United States. When, however, the National Academy of Sciences—National Research Council became the American member, a wider representation was effected that permitted the planning of the Congress that was held in Washington, October 11-15, 1965. This meeting, to the expenses of which the Council made a contribution, brought together more than 1,400 participants from 39 countries. Its proceedings are to be published.

Libraries, Engineering, and Law. Through support to several meetings or conferences the Council assisted in extending

² Edward N. Waters: A library council? *Library Journal* 90: 4002-4004, October 1, 1965.

understanding of the problems of libraries or of library work. In April 1966, the American Academy of Arts and Sciences held a two-day conference to plan a symposium on the research library for its journal *Daedalus*; the proceedings of the conference have been published.³ In May a meeting on the use of sources of information by the engineering professions was held at Lehigh University under the joint sponsorship of the University and the American Society for Engineering Education.⁴ In the last week of June a week-long institute at the University of California at Davis, held under the auspices of the law library, introduced law librarians to the potential applications of computers in their work and gave them opportunities for actual experience in the use of these devices.

³ *Proceedings of the Conference on the Research Library sponsored by Daedalus, Journal of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, and Council on Library Resources, Inc., April 27 and 28, 1966, House of the Academy, Boston, Mass.* [Boston, 1966], 110 p.

⁴ Robert S. Taylor and John M. Carroll: *Summary and recommendations of the ASEE/Lehigh Information Media Conference, May 19-20, 1966.* [Bethlehem, Pa., 1966], 15 p.

“ . . . for the purpose of aiding in the solution
of the problems of libraries . . . ”

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS, 1956-1966

The following list records, under principal topics, the projects assisted by the Council from its first through its tenth year, September 18, 1956 to June 30, 1966. Where available, published reports of projects (with an occasional unpublished report) have been cited, as well as articles and books prepared by project participants. But these citations are in no sense intended to reflect the entire published literature regarding these projects which in some cases has been extensive.

Acquisition of library materials

Association of Research Libraries. Programs for coordinated acquisition of library research materials. 1963; completed. *VIII:21*.*

Far East

Association for Asian Studies. Establishment of a Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center in Taipei, Taiwan. 1965; in progress. *IX:34-35*.

Farmington Plan

Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). Survey and evaluation of the Farmington Plan for the cooperative acquisition by American libraries of foreign publications of potential research value. 1957; completed. *II:21-22; III:30-31*.

* Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports; in this instance the eighth report, page 21.

- Robert L. Talmadge: *The Farmington Plan Survey; an Interim Report. College & Research Libraries* 19:375-383, September 1958.
- Association of Research Libraries: *Farmington Plan Survey, Directed by Robert Vosper & Robert Talmadge, University of Kansas Libraries. Final Report* [Lawrence, Kansas, 1959. 279] p.
- Robert Vosper: *Farmington Redivivus; or Ten Years of Coordinated Foreign Book Procurement in the U.S. Aslib Proceedings* 11:327-34, December 1959.

Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries). *Extension of the Farmington Plan*. 1959; completed. *III:30-31; VI:41*.

- Robert Vosper: *International Book Procurement; or, Farmington Extended, College & Research Libraries* 21:117; March 1960.
- Edwin E. Williams: *Farmington Plan Handbook, Revised to 1961 and Abridged*. [Ithaca, N.Y.: Association of Research Libraries, 1961.] 140 p.

Government publications

American Library Association. *Compilation of a list of non-Government Printing Office federal government publications*. 1963; completed. *VIII:21-22; IX:35-36*.

- Jennings Wood: *United States Government Publications, A Partial List of Non-GPO Imprints, Prepared under the Direction of the Interdivisional Committee on Public Documents of the American Library Association*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1964. 86 p.

Latin America

University of Florida, School of Interamerican Studies, Seminar on the Acquisition of Latin American Materials. *Exploration of the feasibility of a Caribbean bibliographic center*. 1961; completed. *VI:15*.

Photocopying projects

American Council of Learned Societies. *An inquiry into the bases for planning scholarly photocopying projects*. 1960; completed. *IV:17; V:19; VIII:22-23*.

- *Planning for Scholarly Photocopying; A Report Prepared for the American Council of Learned Societies. PMLA, Publications of the Modern-Language-Association-of-America* 79: 1-14, September 1964. Preprinted June 1964.

Library of Congress. Toward expenses of a meeting to plan photocopying of European manuscript sources for American history. 1961; completed. *V:19*.

- Dorothy S. Eaton and Marcia Wright: Conference to Plan Photocopying of European Manuscript Sources for American History. *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 20:209-210, April 10, 1961.
- *Conference on Copying European Manuscript Sources for American History. Woodrow Wilson Room. Library of Congress. Friday, April 7, 1961.* 12 p. processed.

Library of Congress. Development of a national plan for scholarly photocopying. 1964; completed.

———. Establishment of a center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying. 1965, in progress. *IX:24*.

Public Law 480

American Council of Learned Societies. For a report on progress on the implementation of Public Law 480. 1959; completed. *IV:16; V:31*.

- Mortimer Graves: A First Anniversary Report of Progress on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480. *ACLS [American Council of Learned Societies] Newsletter* 10:8-12, November 1959.
- ———: *An Addendum Report on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480.* Key West, Florida; The Author, 1960. 4 p.
- ———: *A Report of Modest Progress in the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to PL 480:* West Newbury, Massachusetts; The Author, 1961. 3 p.

United States Book Exchange

The United States Book Exchange. A re-evaluation of its operations, 1958; completed. *II:22-23; IV:25, 27*.

- Edwin E. Williams: *A Serviceable Reservoir; Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange.* Washington: The Exchange, 1959, 81 p.
- ———: The U.S.B.E. Survey. *Library Resources & Technical Services*, 4:89-91, Winter 1960.

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Society of American Archivists. A study of state archival agencies and programs. 1963; completed. *VI:36-37; IX:11, 39, 48-51*.

- Ernst Posner: *American State Archives*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press [1964]. 397 p. Library of Congress. Travel expenses for French archivists. 1963; completed. *IX:47*.

- Visit of the French Archivists. *The American Archivist* 28: 179, January 1965.

Society of American Archivists. Report on developments following publication of *American State Archives*. 1965; completed. *IX:11*.

- *The Archives and Official Records Programs of the States, Developments Since the Publication of American State Archives*. *IX:48-51*.

U. S. National Archives. Assistance toward an Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives, Washington, May 1966. 1965; completed. *IX:29; X:46*.

- Dorothy S. Eaton and others: The Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives — Washington, D. C., May 9-14, 1966. *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 25:267-75, May 26, 1966.

University of Illinois. Preparation of a manual of university archival practice with respect to records of academic scientific research. 1966; in progress. *X:59*.

Book-circulation

John Diebold & Associates. Inquiry into problems relating to book charging systems. 1959; completed. *IV:20*.

- John Diebold & Associates, Inc.: *Preliminary Study of Library Circulation Systems for the Council on Library Resources, October 1959*. [New York.] 1959. 31 p. (Also issued as a Microcard.)

George Fry & Associates. A study of circulation control in libraries. 1960; completed. *IV:20; V:28, 33-34*.

American Library Association. Advisory services in connection with the study of circulation control in libraries. 1960; completed.

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Publication and implementation of the report of the study of circulation control. 1961; completed. *V:28, 33-34*.

- George Fry & Associates: *Study of Circulation Control Systems, Public Libraries, College and University Libraries, Special Libraries*. Chicago, Library Technology

Project of the American Library Association and the Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1961. 138 p. (Three sections — *Circulation system Selection Manual for Public Libraries*, *Circulation System Selection Manual for College and University Libraries*, *Circulation Control for Special Libraries* — have also been published separately.)

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Construction of a prototype borrower-participation book-charging device (the "Little Giant"). 1961; completed.

———. Preliminary study to develop an academic library book-charging system. 1965; completed. *IX:42*.

———. Evaluation of circulation control systems — IBM 357 equipment and Demco charging machine. June 6, 1966; in progress. *IX:44*.

Book-labeling

American Library Association. Development of a book-marking system, 1959, 1960, 1961, 1962; completed. *IV:16; V:17; VIII:34*.

———. Investigation of adhesives for book-labeling. 1962; completed. *VIII:36*.

- Norman H. Gaber: Book Marking Analysis, *Library Journal* 89:1503-1507, April 1, 1964.
- The Development and Testing of a New Book Marking System. *Ibid.* 89:1911-13, May 1, 1964.
- Gladys T. Piez: Book Marking System Marketed. *ALA Bulletin* 58:410-411, May 1964.
- LTP Book Labeling System Goes to Market. *Ibid.* 58:554-56, June 1964.

Book-selection and evaluation

Meeting to explore the need for and feasibility of a book-selection service for college libraries. 1959; completed. *III:25-26*.

- *Meeting to Explore Some Current and Anticipated Problems in the Building of Book Collections in College Libraries, Edgewater Beach Hotel, Chicago, Illinois. April 20-21, 1959.* [Washington, Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1959] 10 p.
- Report on Conference. *Library Journal* 84:1765-67, June 1, 1959. (Report on the meeting of April 20-21, 1959.)

Expenses of developing a continuing book-selection service for college libraries. 1960, 1961; completed. *IV:15*.

- Hubbard Ballou: Ways to Prepare a "New Shaw" List. In R. E. Kingery and M. F. Tauber, eds.: *Book Catalogs*. New York: Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1963, p. 100-122.

Johns Hopkins University. Interim assistance to *Economics Library Selections* as a book selection service for college libraries. 1960; completed. *V:19*.

- *Economics Library Selections, Series I: New Books in Economics*. Baltimore: Department of Political Economy, The Johns Hopkins University. Quarterly.
- Robert T. Jordan: Economics Library Selections. *Library Journal* 88: 1625-1629, April 15, 1963.

American Library Association. Publication of a book-selection service at the college library level. 1961; in progress. *VI:16; VIII:9, 19-20*.

- *Choice*. Chicago: Association of College and Research Libraries, American Library Association, 1964- , monthly (11 issues a year).

Association of American Law Schools. Preparation of book-selection lists for law school libraries. 1964, 1965; in progress. *VIII:18-19; X:44*.

Various. Publication of the California *List of Books for a College Library* using automatic methods. 1965; completed. *IX:9-10; X:44*.

American Library Association. A list of books for college libraries. 1965; in progress. *X:44*.

Pan American Union. Planning a book-selection list for Latin American University libraries. 1966; in progress. *X:38-39*.

Books—distribution

Pan American Union. A study of obstacles to the free flow of publications (in the book trade) between the American Republics. 1959, 1961; completed. *IV:22; V:31*.

- Peter S. Jennison and William H. Kurth: *Books in the Americas: A Study of the Principal Barriers to the Booktrade in the Americas*. Washington: Pan American Union, 1960. 165 p. (Estudios Bibliotecarios No. 2) Second printing, 1961. Also a Spanish-language edition. *El libro en America*.

Books for the People Fund, Inc. Children's books for Latin America, a feasibility study. 1961; completed. *VI:40-41*.

Books—prediction of use

University of Chicago. Study of patterns in the use of research library materials. 1959; in progress. *III:33; V:31-32; VIII:29*.

- Herman H. Fussler and Julian L. Simon: *Patterns in the Use of Books in Large Research Libraries*. [Chicago:] The University of Chicago Library, 1961. 283, [42] p. Preliminary edition.

Books—preservation and restoration

See also Deterioration/preservation of book stock
Paper

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory

William J. Barrow. Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to the preservation of books and other library materials. 1961, 1963, 1965; in progress. *VI:21-22; VII:20-23; VIII:29-32; IX:31-32; X:47-49*.

- William J. Barrow: Establishing Least Squares Regression Lines for Data of Aged Paper. *TAPPI* (Technical Association of the Pulp and Paper Industry) 45: supp. 209A-210A, September 1962.
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 - I. A two-year research program. 1963, 46 p.
 - II. Test data of naturally aged papers. 1964, 79 p.
 - III. Spray deacidification. 1964, 64 p.
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- ———: Deacidification and Lamination of Deteriorated Documents, 1938-63. *Ibid.* 28:285-90, April 1965.

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Fred W. Alpers, Cleveland, Ohio. Investigation of European library binding practices. 1960; completed. *V:20-21*.

- Fred W. Alpers: *Library Binding in Europe, Submitted to: Council on Library Resources, Inc. . . . Reported on January 16, 1961*. 33 p., typescript.

For a meeting to draft a program for development of performance standards for library binding. 1959; completed. *IV:18*.

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Development of performance standards for library binding, Phase I, 1960; Phase II, 1962, 1963, 1964, 1965. *V:20; VI:22; VII:21-22; VIII:31-32*.

- *Development of Performance Standards for Library Binding, Phase I: Report of the Survey Team*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1961. 62 p.
- Frazer G. Poole: Performance Standards in Library Binding. *Book Production Magazine* 75:67-68, June 1962.
- W. J. Barrow: New Device Tests Performance of Library Bindings. *Book Production Magazine* 79:60-62, March 1964.

William J. Barrow, Richmond, Virginia. Preliminary investigation into aging of adhesives for "perfect" binding. 1961; completed. *V:20; VII:21-22; IX:11-12, 33, 35*.

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American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Design and construction of a cleat sewing machine for rebinding library books. 1964; in progress.

Conservation and repair

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Testing of certain adhesives and other materials used in book and manuscript preservation and repair. 1959; completed. *IV:18; V:18*.

- Gladys T. Piez: Laminator for Libraries. *ALA Bulletin* 53:269-75, March 1961.

- [American Library Association. Library Technology Project:] Evaluation of GBC [General Binding Corporation] Laminator. *Ibid.* 56:56-57, January 1962.
- ———: Manuscript-marking Ink: *Ibid.* 56:361, April 1962.
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American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Preparation of a manual on the conservation of library materials — Phase I. 1965; in progress. *X*:56.

Books for the blind

Library of Congress. Pilot project demonstration of production of encapsuled tape-recorded books for the blind. 1960; completed. *V*:25; *VIII*:27-28.

- CBS Laboratories, Columbia Broadcasting System: *Tape Duplicator for Magnetic Talking Books. Final Report - Instruction Manual. Report No. CLD-1518 . . . Prepared for Library of Congress* [46] p., 11 plates, 29 cm.

Recording for the Blind, Inc. Pilot project demonstration of service of encapsuled tape-recorded books for the blind. 1960; in progress. *V*:25; *VIII*:27-28.

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- Recording for the Blind, Inc., New York: *Final Report, Cartridge Tape Player*, New York, 1964, 3 p., Ill. Typescript.

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Permanence/durability

American Library Association. For testing catalog card stock. 1960; completed. *V*:17; *VI*:20.

- W. J. Barrow: *Permanence and Durability of Library Catalog Cards*, Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association [1961]. 39 p.

Reproduction

The de Florez Company. Design and construction of a prototype stencil catalog card duplicator. 1960, 1962; completed. *IV*:15-16; *V*:17.

American Library Association. Catalog card reproduction; a systems study. 1961; completed. *V:17; IX:26, 42.*

- *Catalog Card Reproduction.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association 1965. 82 p.

Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Design of an automatic catalog card replicator. 1961; completed. *V:17; VI:20-21.*

- Richard E. Dolbear: *A Programmed Printer for the High-Speed Production of Catalog Card Sets.* Boston: Edger-ton, Germeshausen & Grier, Inc. 1962. 68 p.

Fairchild Camera and Instrument Corporation. Davidson Division. A feasibility study of making a short-run litho-graphic master for duplicating library catalog cards. 1962; completed.

Capital Graphic Systems, Inc. A feasibility study of a duplicating process for library cards using the lithographic principle. 1963, 1964; completed.

Cataloging

Nasser Sharify. Towards a cataloging code for Persian library materials. 1957, 1958; completed. *II:11. III:25; V:16-17.*

American Library Association. Assistance in publishing Sharify's *Cataloging of Persian Works.* 1959-61; completed. *III:25; V:16-17.*

- Nasser Sharify: *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description.* Chi-cago; American Library Association 1959. 161 p. Second printing, 1961.

American Library Association, Assistance toward ALA Cata-log Code revision project. 1960, 1961, 1962, 1965; in progress. *V:16; VII:16; VIII:14-15; IX:16; X:38.*

Stanford University. A survey of methods of producing library catalogs in book form. 1963; completed. *VIII:13-14.*

- R. M. Hayes and R. M. Shoffner: *The Economics of Book Catalog Production, A Study Prepared for Stanford Uni-versity Libraries . . .* [Sherman Oaks, California: Ad-vanced Information Systems Division, Hughes Dynamics, Inc.] 1964, 110 p.

Association of Research Libraries. Survey of original cata-logging performed in American research libraries. 1964, 1965; completed. *VIII:15-16; IX:18.*

- James E. Skipper: The characteristics of cataloging in research libraries. *In Association of Research Libraries: Minutes* 68:55-85, July 9, 1966.

Various. Coordination of cataloging rules between libraries and governmental documentation centers. 1964; completed. *VIII:15*.

Columbia University. Development of a cataloging code for materials in Pushto, Urdu and Panjabi. 1965; in progress. *X:45*.

New York Public Library. Investigation of the problems of research library catalog renovation, presentation and maintenance. 1965; in progress. *X:43*.

Cataloging at source

Library of Congress. Preliminary investigation of the feasibility of "cataloging at source." 1958; completed. *II:15-18*.

- Andrew D. Osborn: *Cataloging at the Source; an Opportunity for Cooperation Between the Four Major Book Arts*. Chicago: American Library Association 1958. 18 p. Typescript.

Library of Congress. Demonstration of "Cataloging at Source." 1958; completed. *II:15-18; IV:24-25*.

- U.S. Library of Congress, Processing Department: Cataloging in Source. *Cataloging Service* 48:1-3, September 1958; 50:1-4, November 1958; 53:1-17, June 1959.
- *The Cataloging-in-Source Experiment. A Report to The Librarian of Congress* by the Director of the Processing Department. 1960. 199 p.

National Library of Australia. Investigation of cataloging at source. 1965; completed.

International coordination

American Library Association. Toward the international coordination of cataloging rules. 1957; completed. *I:26-28; II:10*.

- Andrew D. Osborn: At a German Library Conference. *ALA Bulletin* 51:773-75, November 1957.
- ———: Zur Revision der Instruktionen für die Katalogisierung an Amerikanischen Bibliotheken: Vortrag. Gehalten auf dem Bibliothekartag in Lübeck am 13 Juni

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American Library Association. For travel grants to promote the international coordination of cataloging rules. 1958, 1959; completed. *II:10-11; IV:13; VI:13*.

International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA). For a preliminary meeting to plan an international conference on the principles of cataloging. 1958; completed. *II:10-11; IV:23*.

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- ———: Report, *Libri* 9:254-61.

International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA). Assistance toward an International Conference on Cataloging Principles, Paris, October 1961. 1959; completed. *IV:13, 23; VI:12-13*.

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- International Cataloging Conference. 1961. *Ibid.* 14:136, May-June 1960.
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- ———: *Report*. London: [Organizing Committee of the Conference] 1963. 293 p.
- Wyllis E. Wright: International Cataloging Conference. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 4:85-89, Winter 1960.
- Susan M. Haskins: Moving Toward International Cataloging Agreement. *ALA Bulletin* 54:197-201. March 1960.

American Library Association. Travel expenses in connection with the International Conference on Cataloging Principles, 1961. 1961; completed.

Music Library Association. Travel expenses in connection with the International Conference on Cataloging principles, Paris, 1961. 1961; completed.

———: Representation in meetings of the International Cataloging Code Commission of the International Music Library Association, 1964, 1965; completed. *VIII:15; IX:16; X:38.*

Coding of publications

American Library Association. Inquiry into the feasibility of developing a numerical code for identifying and characterizing current American publications. 1960; completed. *IV:15; V:30-31; VI:17.*

- G. A. Harrer and Alex Ladenson: Report on the Project to Investigate the Feasibility of a National Code Number System for Current Publications. N.p., April 1961. 25 p.
- ———: A Proposal for a National Code Number System for Current Publications. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 6:4-12, Winter 1962.

Cooperative book-processing centers

Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. Demonstration of cooperative/centralized processing for small independent public libraries. 1957; completed. *II:18-19; III:44-45.*

- Willard K. Dennis: Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. *Missouri Library Association Quarterly* 18:119-23, December 1957.
- ———: Central Processing in Southwest Missouri, *Library Journal* 84:3378-80, November 1, 1959.
- ———: A Unique Cataloging and Processing Centre (USA). *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* 14:173-4, July-August 1960.

American Library Association. A review and evaluation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. 1958, 1960; completed. *II:18-19; III:44-45; V:18; VI:16-17.*

- Orcena Mahoney: An Experiment in Cooperative Processing. *ALA Bulletin* 52:127-30, February 1958.
- Brigitte L. Kenney: Centralized Processing—Missouri Style. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 2:185-98, Summer, 1958.

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- Frances Dukes Carhart: *Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.; a Study in Cooperative Centralized Technical Services.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1962. 78 p.

Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. For an exhibit of the Service's work at the conference of the American Library Association-Canadian Library Association, Montreal, 1960; completed. *IV:16*.

Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado. An experimental study to determine the feasibility of cooperative technical processing for academic libraries. 1961; completed. *VI:39; VII:32*.

- Donald E. Oehlerts: *A Study to Determine the Feasibility of Establishing a Cooperative Technical Processing Program and Direct Transmission of Interlibrary Loans.* Denver, Colorado: Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado, 1962. 45 p.

Copying

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New York Public Library (on behalf of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying). For legal studies of photocopying in libraries. 1959, 1961; completed. *III:38; V:32; VIII:37*.

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- ———: Fair Use in Photocopying. Report on Single Copies. *ALA Bulletin* 55:571-3, June 1961.
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Committee to Investigate Copyright Problems Affecting Communication (CICP). Feasibility study of a copyright clearing house in connection with permissions for photoreproduction. 1963; completed *VIII:37*.

Equipment—development

Eugene Garfield Associates (later, Institute for Scientific Information). For development of the "Copywriter." 1958, 1963; completed. *III:38; IV:30; VII:28; VIII:26*.

- [Eugene Garfield Associates:] *Final Report on the Development of a First Model of the Copywriter*. Philadelphia, 1960. 11 p., typescript.
- Institute for Scientific Information: *Feasibility Study & Report on Copywriter*, Philadelphia, 1963. 18 p.

W. C. Huebner. For a demonstration model of Migrafax. 1958; completed. *V:22*.

The de Florez Company. Development of a pilot model of a book-copying cradle. 1961, 1962, 1963; in progress.

Equipment—development—the cataloger's camera

Radio Corporation of America. Working model of a "cataloger's camera." 1958; completed. *II:14-15; III:29; V:17*.

- Radio Corporation of America. Defense Electronic Products Division: *Final Report. Automatic Enlarging Instant Copy Camera*. [Camden: The Corporation, 1959.] 6 p. 4 pl.

Indiana University Foundation, Indiana University. Development and testing of a camera for cataloger's use. 1964; completed. *IX:27; X:40*.

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Equipment—development—The Scholar's Camera

Bell & Howell Company. Fabrication of the prototypes of a scholar's camera. 1961; completed. *V:24-25; VI:30-31; VIII:25*.

Photogrammetry, Inc. Design and fabrication of prototypes of a scholar's camera and monocular viewer. 1963; completed. *VII:28*; *VIII:25-26*.

Equipment—evaluation

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Testing of book-copying equipment. Photocopying from bound volumes. Full-size copying from microtext. 1960, 1961, 1962, 1963, 1966. *V:22*; *VI:31*; *VII:25, 38*; *VIII:34*.

- William R. Hawken: *Photocopying from Bound Volumes; A Study of Machines, Methods and Materials*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1962. 208 p. Supplements 1-3, 1963, 1964, 1964.
- ———: *Enlarged Prints from Library Microforms. A Study of Processes, Equipment and Materials*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association [1963]. 131 p.

Manual

American Library Association. Library Technology Project. Preparation of a manual on methods of reproducing research materials. 1964; in progress. *VIII:35*; *X:55*.

Materials and methods

Lyman Chalkley. Investigation of dye cyanides and other dry-process photosensitive materials. 1958; completed. *III:38*.

- Lyman Chalkley: Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials. *Photographic Science and Engineering* 3:174-77, July-August 1959.

Deterioration/preservation of library book-stock

See also Books—preservation and restoration
Paper

Randolph W. Church. Inquiry to develop a plan of investigation of the life-expectancy of books in U.S. libraries. 1961; completed. *V:21-22*; *VI:22-23*.

- Randolph W. Church: *Inquiry to Develop a Plan of Investigation of the Life-Expectancy of Books in United States Libraries. Sampling of Library of Congress Union Catalog File Cards*. [Richmond, 1961.] 9, 20 p.

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for the preservation of research library materials. 1961, 1962; completed. *V:21-22*; *VI:22-23*.

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- Association of Research Libraries. Committee on Preservation of Research Library Materials: *The Preservation of Deteriorating Books; An Examination of the Problem with Recommendations for a Solution*, prepared for the Committee by Gordon Williams. N. p., 1964. 33p.
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- David W. Heron and J. Richard Blanchard: Seven League Boots for the Scholar? Problems and Prospects of Library Telefacsimile. *Library Journal* 91:3601-3605, August 1966.

University of California, Berkeley. Planning an experiment in library application of telefacsimile. 1966; in Progress. *X:49*.

Financial Statements

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

September 14, 1966

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1966 and its expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Exhibit I

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1966

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 282,065
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximates market)	\$1,167,953	
Savings account	256,424	
Certificates of deposit, at cost plus accrued interest	<u>732,580</u>	2,156,957
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in annual installments of \$1,000,000 (Note)		2,000,000
Deposits		<u>488</u>
		<u>\$4,439,510</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see Exhibit III)	\$ 841,546
Accounts payable and withheld taxes	2,208
Fund balance:	
Balance June 30, 1965	\$4,649,101
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year (see Exhibit II)	<u>1,053,345</u>
Balance June 30, 1966 (Note)	<u>3,595,756</u>
	<u>\$4,439,510</u>

NOTE

The installment for the year ended June 30, 1966 was received on July 1, 1965. The installment for the year ending June 30, 1967 was received on June 14, 1966. The terms of the Grant from The Ford Foundation provide that \$200,000 annually is earmarked to assist the Council "to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel." At June 30, 1966 \$848,091 of the Fund balance is earmarked for this purpose. Also, \$344,198 has been appropriated for other specific grants and contracts and \$25,000 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts to be made at his discretion.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Exhibit II

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1966

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (see Exhibit III)	\$1,150,075	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see Exhibit III)	<u>196,972</u>	\$ 953,103
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	140,969	
Rent	10,800	
Professional services	2,826	
Travel and meetings	10,906	
Furniture and equipment	499	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	<u>17,278</u>	<u>183,278</u>
		\$1,136,381

INCOME

From investments	82,536	
From gift	<u>500</u>	<u>83,036</u>
Expenditures less income		<u><u>\$1,053,345</u></u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Exhibit III

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS
AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1966

	Payable June 30, 1965	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1966
American Academy of Arts and Sciences					
Assistance in planning an issue of Daedalus devoted to research libraries		\$ 2,500		\$ 2,500	
American Association of Junior Colleges					
Support of a meeting on junior college libraries, Spring 1965			\$ 104	(104)	
American Association of Law Libraries					
Advisory Committee on Project Lawsearch			32	(32)	
American Institute of Biological Sciences					
Continuation of experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform			800	(800)	
American Library Association					
A book list for college libraries		45,000		45,000	
A study of systems of public libraries		50,460			\$ 50,460
Completion of Anglo-American Cataloging Rules ..	\$ 7,931			7,931	
Compilation of a list of non-Government Printing Office Federal Government Publications			1,003	(1,003)	
Library Technology Project					
Development of performance standards for library bookbinding—Phase II		14,022		14,022	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965	52,031			44,531	7,500
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1966	130,000			130,000	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1966	100,000			78,354	21,646
Extension of Library Technology Project to August 31, 1967		105,829			105,829
Projects of testing and standardization to August 31, 1967		162,503			162,503
Publication of a book-selection service (Choice) at the college library level	50,000			50,000	
Support of the ALA International Relations Office	22,497		4,568	17,929	
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries)					
Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings	12,000		23,147	(11,147)	
American Standards Association					
For an ISO-IFLA-UNESCO meeting on standards for library statistics, The Hague, November 1965		2,130		2,130	

	Payable June 30, 1965	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1966
Association of American Law Schools					
Preparation of book selection lists for law school libraries	\$27,000	\$30,000		\$57,000	
Association for Asian Studies, Inc.					
Establishment of a Chinese materials and research aids service center in Taiwan	5,000			5,000	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to the preservation of books and other library materials	20,257	160,200	\$5,387	76,615	\$98,455
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	14,090			5,020	9,070
Columbia University					
Development of a cataloging code for materials in Pushto, Urdu and Panjabi		5,175		5,175	
Council of National Library Associations, Inc.					
Program development		1,000		106	894
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Field test of automatic book-cradle/page turner ..	1,333		1,333		
Working model of a book-copying cradle/press ..	929		929		
Working model of a catalog card duplicator	2,314		2,314		
Documentation, Inc.					
Development of a portable inexpensive reader-printer for microcopies	10,000	7,000	2,000	15,000	
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature*	3,178			1,062	2,116
Houston Fearless Corporation					
Delivery of a prototype of a step-and-repeat filmcard camera-processor	63,000		1,000	62,000	
Field test of camera-processor at University of California, Los Angeles		7,443			7,443
Inforonics, Inc.					
Study of mechanization of filing rules	3,350			3,350	
Intectron Incorporated					
Investigation of factors affecting high-reduction microphotography	733		733		
International Business Machines Corporation					
Pilot project for conversion of National Union Catalog to machine-readable form	10,200			10,200	
International Micrographic Congress					
Preparation and publication of an International Guide to Microfilm Equipment		10,000		7,000	3,000
Lehigh University					
For a preliminary meeting on use of engineering media, sources and systems in engineering education		1,000		1,000	

* Council-administered project.

	Payable June 30, 1965	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1966
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections (supplement)	\$35,565			\$35,565	
Establishment of a center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying	75,300			25,100	\$50,200
Establishment of a National Register of Microform Masters office and publication of first volume of information collected	17,500			17,500	
Next steps to commencement of distribution of Library of Congress cataloging information in machine-readable form		\$130,000		97,500	32,500
Services of the U. S. Government Printing Office in connection with the investigation of the creation of a machine record of Library of Congress catalog data	5,000		\$10,000	(5,000)	
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries	20,000		20,000		
Support of the work of the Federal Library Committee (supplement)		87,650		22,550	65,100
Los Angeles County Public Library					
Investigation of the use of optical character recognition equipment in library operations		38,000		19,000	19,000
Meeting to discuss a format for the conversion of bibliographic data to machine-readable form for computer processing*	389		389		
Michigan State University					
Cost comparison of three methods of converting bibliographical information to machine-readable form		59,823		29,912	29,911
Mississippi Research and Development Center, Information Services Division					
Study of the feasibility of establishing a a state-wide union catalog of library holdings in Mississippi		2,000			2,000
National Archives and Records Service					
Assistance toward an Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives, Washington, D. C., 1966	35,500	5,205		40,705	
National Bureau of Standards					
Experiments in automatic indexing			116	(116)	
Study and experimentation in computer composition of library materials		25,000		25,000	
National Library of Australia					
Investigation of cataloging at source		2,000	138	1,862	
New York Metropolitan Reference and Research Library Agency, Inc.					
Coordination of reference-research library work in Metropolitan New York		37,000		10,000	27,000
New York Public Library					
Investigation of the problems of research library catalog renovation, presentation and maintenance		40,000		40,000	

* Council-administered project.

	Payable June 30, 1965	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1966
Pan American Union					
Compilation and publication of a subject heading list in Spanish	\$12,500			\$12,500	
Planning a book selection list for Latin American university libraries		\$1,200		1,200	
Anne Pellowski					
Assistance in the compilation of a world bibliography of sources of information on literature and libraries for children		3,885		3,885	
Publication of a book selection list—various*	126,125		\$122,979	3,146	
Republic Aviation Division, Fairchild Hiller					
Analysis and verification program for utilizing the Micro-Vue System for reducing the cost of distribution of library materials		65,770			\$65,770
C. Walter Stone					
A study to assist toward the development of library services for the planned community of Columbia, Howard County, Maryland		4,750		4,750	
University of California					
Preparation and publication of a handbook on data processing for libraries	68,498			34,249	34,249
University of California at Berkeley					
Planning an experiment in library application of telefacsimile		2,080		2,080	
University of California at Davis					
Institute on computer science for law libraries, Davis, June 26 - July 2, 1966		10,000		10,000	
University of California at Los Angeles					
To test and evaluate, in practical application, a step-and-repeat camera developed for CLR by Houston Fearless Corporation		3,000		3,000	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Illinois					
Preparation of a manual of university archival practice with respect to records of academic scientific research		10,000			10,000
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation		18,450		6,150	12,300
	<u>\$956,820</u>	<u>\$1,150,075</u>	<u>\$196,972</u>	<u>\$1,068,377</u>	<u>\$841,546</u>

* Council-administered project.

A C K N O W L E D G M E N T S

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the cover, is reproduced from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The picture has appeared in the Council's Third and subsequent annual reports.

A book-wheel was included in the Mexican exhibition at the New York World's Fair, where it was described as an eighteenth century fascitol, Coll. Museo Nacional de Historia, Mexico City. The wheel is about five feet high and two feet wide. The photograph is by Mr. Gordon P. Martin, Librarian, Sacramento State College.

A book-wheel in the St. Nicholas Parish Church, Yarmouth, England, was pictured in Harper's *New Monthly Magazine* for June 1882 (LXV:7), and was called to the Council's attention by Mr. Sol M. Malkin, Editor and Publisher of *Antiquarian Bookman*. The book-wheel, which may have belonged to the sixteenth century, was lost when the Church was destroyed in the course of an incendiary air raid in 1942, according to Mr. A. A. C. Hedges, F.L.A., Borough Librarian and Curator, Great Yarmouth. Books in his collection indicate that the book-wheel "had six shelves with an aggregate length of $23\frac{3}{4}$ feet, and was arranged by machinery (within the sides were nine wheels revolving around a fixed central one; three in the first course, six in the second, *i.e.*, one connected with each shelf), and that the shelves severally maintained one angle whilst all else was revolving . . . the two discs between which the six shelves were suspended measured three feet eight inches in diameter."

The Chinese version of the scholar and book-wheel appeared in the Council's Sixth Annual Report. The picture is taken from a copy of the 1895-1898 edition, in the Library of Congress, of the *Ku chin t'u shu chi ch'êng*, which is a reprint of an eighteenth century work which took the picture from the *Yüan hsi ch'i t'u shuo*. This last named work was a collaboration by Father Jean Terrenz, S.J. (1576-1630), and a Chinese scholar, Wang Cheng.

The French version of the book-wheel, which appeared in the Council's Ninth Annual Report, is taken from *Recueil d'ouvrages curieux de mathématique et de mécanique, ou, Description du cabinet de Monsieur Grollier de Serviere* . . . Lyon, 1719. It was called to the Council's attention by Mr. Frederick R. Goff, Chief of the Rare Book Division, Library of Congress.

This Tenth Annual Report was designed by the George Lohr Studio. The type, Bodoni Book, was set by Hodges Type, Inc. The Report was printed, by offset, by Moore & Moore, Inc., and printed on "Permalife," a stable and enduring paper produced by the Standard Paper Manufacturing Company, Richmond, Virginia.

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